

Republic of Iraq
Ministry of Higher Education
and Scientific Research
Middle Technical University
Electrical Engineering Technical
College

Hybrid Lightweight Cryptographic Algorithms for Wireless Sensor Networks

A THESIS

SUBMITTED TO THE ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING
TECHNICAL COLLEGE, MIDDLE TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY
IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR
THE DEGREE OF MASTER OF SCIENCE IN COMPUTER
ENGINEERING TECHNIQUES

Submitted by

Hudhaifa Abdulmunem Abdulhameed

Supervised by

Prof. Dr. Mahmood F. Mosleh

Asst. Prof. Alhamzah T. Mohammed

January 2022

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

﴿وَلَقَدْ آتَيْنَا دَاوُودَ وَسُلَيْمَانَ عِلْمًا
وَقَالَا الْحَمْدُ لِلَّهِ الَّذِي فَضَّلَنَا عَلَى
كَثِيرٍ مِّنْ عِبَادِهِ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ﴾

[النمل: 15]

Certification

I certify this thesis titled “**Hybrid Lightweight Cryptographic Algorithms for Wireless Sensor Networks**” which is being submitted by **Hudhaifa Abdulmunem Abdulhameed** was prepared under my supervision at the Electrical Engineering Technical College in a partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of master of Computer Engineering Techniques.

Signature:

Name: **Prof. Dr. Mahmood F. Mosleh**

Date: / /

Signature:

Name: **Asst. Prof. Alhamzah T. Mohammed**

Date: / /

Linguist Certification

I certify that I have read this thesis titled “**A proposed Lightweight Data Security for Wireless Sensor Network Applications**” prepared by **Hudhaifa Abdulmunem Abdulhameed**, and corrected any grammatical mistake I found.

Signature:

Name: **Asst. Prof. Dr. Raghad Hassan Hussein**

Date: / /

Head of the Department of Computer Engineering Techniques

In view of available recommendation, I found this thesis for debate by the examination committee.

Signature:

Name: **Asst. Prof. Dr. Mohammed Ibrahim Shugaa**

Date: / /

Certification

We are the members of examining committee certify that after reading this thesis titled “**Hybrid Lightweight Cryptographic Algorithms for Wireless Sensor Networks**” and examining the student **Hudhaifa Abdulmunem Abdulhameed** in its contents, think it is adequate for the award for the degree of master of science in Computer Engineering Techniques.

Signature:

Name: Prof. Dr. Raad H. Thaher

Title: Chairman

Date: 2022/ /

Signature:

Name: Prof. Dr. Mahmood F. Mosleh

Title: Supervisor

Date: 2022/ /

Signature:

Name: Asst. Prof. Dr. Faiza A. Abd

Title: Member

Date: 2022/ /

Signature:

Name: Asst. Prof. Alhamzah T. Mohammed

Title: Supervisor

Date: 2022/ /

Signature:

Name: Dr. Mohammed J. Zaiter

Title: Member

Date: 2022/ /

Approval of the Electrical Engineering Technical College

Signature:

Name: Prof. Dr. Adel Ahmed Obed

Title: Dean of Electrical Engineering Technical College

Date: 2022/ /

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work in this thesis is my own except for quotations and summaries which have been duly acknowledged.

9/1/2022

Hudhaifa Abdulmunem Abdulhameed

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

In the name of Allah, the most merciful and gracious, for giving me the determination and will to complete this research work.

I appreciate the guideline and inspirations that I have received from my supervisors **Prof. Dr. Mahmood Farhan Mosleh** and **Asst. Prof. Alhamzah T. Mohammad** for their pieces of guidance, advice, and encouragement, without their continuous interest and support, this work would not have been the same as presented here.

I am most grateful to my mother, father, wife, and brothers for their continuous support, encouragement, care, love, and patience throughout my studies.

ABSTRACT

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are a massive number of tiny nodes installed in harsh and hostile environments to monitor and gather specific data. WSNs are installed to support bridge structures, healthcare, robotics, environmental monitoring, etc. WSNs have unique restrictions such as severe energy, denser level of node deployment, higher unreliability of sensor nodes, computation, and storage constraints. These characteristics must be considered before making any modifications. The problem with the data transmission of WSNs is that they are vulnerable to different attacks, so they need to be encrypted. Many cryptographic algorithms play a good role in data security for WSNs with considering their characteristics. Cryptography has two techniques for confidentiality: the symmetric-key and asymmetric-key techniques. But there are still some problems. For example, to store the key across all nodes in the network, the symmetric-key technique needs more storage, while the asymmetric-key technique takes more computation time. So, it must be modified to fit the WSN specifications.

In this thesis, three hybrid cryptographic algorithms have been proposed, which are: LZ4–ECDH–Blowfish–MD5 (LEBM), LZ4–ECDH–Blowfish–RC4–MD5 (LEBRM), and LZ4–ECDH–Blowfish–RC4–AES–MD5 (LEBRAM). To provide a high-security level with low power consumption.

The proposed algorithms achieve three cryptographic objectives: confidentiality, authentication, and integrity by using the Blowfish, Rivest Cipher 4 (RC4), and Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) algorithms for encryption; the Elliptic Curve Diffie Hellman (ECDH) algorithm for key distribution; and the Message Digest 5 (MD5) hashing algorithm for data integrity. In addition, the Lempel Ziv 4 (LZ4) compression algorithm is used to reduce the plaintext size, which leads to reducing the processing time and power consumption.

The ciphertext size, encryption and decryption times, and throughput of the proposed algorithms were calculated. Also, the Diehard test was applied to the proposed algorithms. Accordingly, the results were compared with those of previously published works. Each proposed algorithm was tested using two computers labeled "A and B" and the Raspberry Pi. When using the Raspberry Pi, the results show that LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM achieved the best results compared to previous works. LEBRAM has 120 p -values in the safe area and only 37 p -values in the failure area, which is the highest security level. In addition, when the plaintext is 184,162 B, it has the least processing time with an encryption time of 303.1 ms and a decryption time of 319.5 ms, which makes it ideal for large plaintexts. On the other hand, when the plaintext is 609 B, the LEBRM algorithm has the least processing time, with an encryption time of 164.5 ms and a decryption time of 71.5 ms, which makes it ideal for small plaintexts. Additionally, LEBM is the simplest to implement.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION	i
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	ii
ABSTRACT	iii
TABLE OF CONTENTS	iv
LIST OF FIGURES	vii
LIST OF TABLES	ix
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	xi
LIST OF SYMBOLS	xiii
LIST OF PUBLICATION	xiv
CHAPTER ONE GENERAL INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. Introduction	1
1.2. Literature Survey	3
1.3. Problems Statement	7
1.4. Aim of the Work	7
1.5. Thesis Contributions	8
1.6. Thesis Outlines	8
CHAPTER TWO THEORETICAL BACKGROUND	10
2.1. Introduction	10
2.2. The Benefits of WSN Security	10
2.2.1. Security Objectives	11
2.2.2. Attacks and Attackers	11
2.3. Lightweight Cryptography (LWC) for WSN	12
2.4. Symmetric-key Techniques	13
2.4.1. Advantages of Symmetric-key Techniques	15
2.4.2. Disadvantages of Symmetric-key Techniques	15
2.4.3. RC4 Algorithm	16

2.4.4. Blowfish Algorithm	17
2.4.5. AES Algorithm	18
2.4.6. Cipher Modes	19
2.5. Asymmetric-key Techniques	20
2.6. Hashing Functions	23
2.7. Compression Algorithms	26
2.8. Randomness Test	29
2.9. Raspberry Pi as a WSN Node	32
CHAPTER THREE THE PROPOSED HYBRID ALGORITHMS	33
3.1. Introduction	33
3.2. LEBM Hybrid Algorithm	33
3.2.1. The LEBM Encryption Process	33
3.2.2. The LEBM Decryption Process	35
3.3. LEBRM Hybrid Algorithm	37
3.3.1. The LEBRM Encryption Process	37
3.3.2. The LEBRM Decryption Process	38
3.4. LEBRAM Hybrid Algorithm	38
3.4.1. The LEBRAM Encryption Process	38
3.4.2. The LEBRAM Decryption Process	41
CHAPTER FOUR RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS	44
4.1. Introduction	44
4.2. The Ciphertext Size	45
4.3. The Encryption Time	46
4.4. The Decryption Time	49
4.5. The Throughput	53
4.6. The Diehard Tests	56
4.7. The Benefits of Using the LZ4 Compression Algorithm	59

CHAPTER FIVE CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK	62
5.1. Conclusions	62
5.2. Future Work	62
REFERENCES	64
APPENDICES	72
Appendix A: publications' Acceptance Letters	A1
Appendix B: Technical specifications of the Raspberry Pi 4 Model B	B1
Appendix C: The Proposed Algorithms	C1

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No.	Figure Caption	Page
1.1	An example of small WSN	2
2.1	Lightweight cryptographic algorithm design tradeoff	13
2.2	The symmetric encryption process explanation	14
2.3	RC4 algorithm's flowchart	16
2.4	Basic Structure of Blowfish	17
2.5	Basic Structure of AES	18
2.6	CBC mode encryption flowchart	19
2.7	CBC mode decryption flowchart	19
2.8	Public-key cryptosystem in WSNs	20
2.9	The procedure of the ECDH algorithm	23
2.10	A single operation within a round of MD5	26
3.1	The LEBM encryption flowchart	35
3.2	The LEBM decryption flowchart	36
3.3	The LEBRM encryption flowchart	39
3.4	The LEBRM decryption flowchart	40
3.5	The LEBRAM encryption flowchart	42
3.6	The LEBRAM decryption flowchart	43
4.1	A comparison of ciphertext sizes (bytes) between the proposed and previously presented algorithms	46
4.2	A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms	47
4.3	A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms	48

4.4	A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms	49
4.5	A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms	50
4.6	A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms	51
4.7	A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms	52
4.8	A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms	54
4.9	A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms	55
4.10	A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms	56
4.11	p -values distribution for the plaintext	57
4.12	p -values distribution for the LEBM	57
4.13	p -values distribution for the LEBRM	58
4.14	p -values distribution for the LEBRAM	58
4.15	A comparison of Diehard results between the proposed algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) and the previously presented MECC algorithm	59
4.16	A comparison between the use of LZ4 with LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM and without using any compression algorithm	61

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Table Caption	Page
2.1	The Diehard Test's limits of safe, doubt, and failure areas	32
4.1	A comparison of the hardware specifications between the used computers	44
4.2	A comparison of the software specifications between the used computers	45
4.3	A comparison of ciphertext sizes (bytes) between the proposed and previously presented algorithms	45
4.4	A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms	46
4.5	A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms	47
4.6	A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms	48
4.7	A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms	50
4.8	A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms	51
4.9	A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms	52
4.10	A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms	53
4.11	A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms	54
4.12	A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms	55
4.13	A comparison of Diehard results between the proposed algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) and the previously presented MECC algorithm	58

4.14	(a) Ciphertext size, encryption time, and decryption time for the LEBM algorithm without any compression algorithm (b) Ciphertext size, encryption time, and decryption time for the LEBM algorithm using the LZ4 compression algorithm	59
4.15	A comparison between the use of LZ4 with LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM and without using any compression algorithm	60

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

3D	Three-Dimensional
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
BS	Base Station
CBC	Cipher Block Chaining
CHF	Cryptographic Hash Function
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSI	Camera Serial Interface
DES	Data Encryption Standard
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
DoS	Denial of Service
DSI	Display Serial Interface
ECC	Elliptic Curve Cryptography
ECDH	Elliptic curve Diffie Hellman
ECDSA	Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm
EECA	Energy Efficient Cryptographic Algorithm
GA	Genetic Algorithm
GPIO	General Purpose Input/Output
HA	Hybrid Algorithm
HCA	Hybrid Cryptography Algorithm
HDMI	High-Definition Multimedia Interface
IAES	Improved Advanced Encryption Standard
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group
LEBM	LZ4–ECDH–Blowfish–MD5
LEBRAM	LZ4–ECDH–Blowfish–RC4–AES–MD5
LEBRM	LZ4–ECDH–Blowfish–RC4–MD5
LWC	Lightweight Cryptography
LZ4	Lempel Ziv 4

MACs	Message Authentication Codes
MD5	Message Digest 5
MECC	Multiple Elliptic Curve Cryptography
MicroSD	Micro Secure Digital
MIPI	Mobile Industry Processor Interface
MP3	MPEG audio Layer-3
MPEG	Moving Picture Experts Group
OPSO	Overlapping Pairs Sparse Occupancy
OQSO	Overlapping Quadruples Sparse Occupancy
PNG	Pseudo Random Number Generators
PoE	Power over Ethernet
QoS	Quality of Service
RAM	Random Access Memory
RC4	Rivest Cipher 4
RF	Radio Frequency
RSA	Rivest Shamir Adleman
SDRAM	Synchronous Dynamic Random Access Memory
SHA	Secure Hashing Algorithms
SNs	Sensor Nodes
SoC	programmable System On a Chip
THCA	Two-phase Hybrid Cryptography Algorithm
TTPs	Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures
USB	Universal Serial Bus
VLSI	Very Large Scale Integration
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
WSNs	Wireless Sensor Networks

LIST OF SYMBOLS

A, B, C, D	A set of predefined constants
bi	Number of blocks
d_A	Alice private key
d_B	Bob private key
Et	Encryption time
F, G, H, I	Non-linear functions
G	The generator
h	The cofactor
i	Counter
Ki	A 32-bit constant
Mi	A 32-bit block of the message's input data
n	Integer number
P	A random point
p -value	The result of the Diehard test
Q_A	Alice Public key
Q_B	Bob Public key
s	Left bit rotation
Tp	Total plaintext
η	The subgroup size

LIST OF PUBLICATION

- **Hudhaifa A. Abdulhameed**, Ayoub A. Abdulhameed, Mahmood F. Mosleh, and Alhamzah T. Mohammed, “Lightweight Security Protocol for WSNs using Hybrid Cryptography Algorithm”, accepted in the International Conference on Applied Science and Technology (ICAST), AIP Publishing, Karbala, Iraq, 2021.
- **Hudhaifa A. Abdulhameed**, Mahmood F. Mosleh, Alhamzah T. Mohammed, and Ayoub A. Abdulhameed, "A lightweight hybrid cryptographic algorithm for WSN security using the raspberry pi as a node", accepted in the Iraqi Academics Syndicate 2nd International Conference for Pure and Applied Sciences (IICPS), Journal of Physics: Conference Series publishing, Babylon, Iraq, 2021.
- **Hudhaifa A. Abdulhameed**, Hadel F. Abdalmaaen, Alhamzah T. Mohammed, Mahmood F. Mosleh, and Ayoub A. Abdulhameed, "A lightweight hybrid cryptographic algorithm for WSNs tested by the Diehard tests and the Raspberry Pi", under consideration in the 2022 International Conference on Computer Science and Software Engineering (CSASE), IEEE publishing, Duhok, Iraq, 2022.

CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

In the 1970s, the early systems of Sensor Nodes (SNs) were mostly wired and tiny, but the new idea of networks and distributed sensors led to their employment in military and industrial applications. In the 1990s, Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) design became practical for wireless technologies and low power consumption. Researchers initially considered wireless sensor applications and the inspection of large Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) [1].

Continuous technological advancement allows us to envision a future in which many energy-efficient and inexpensive SNs are densely deployed across the physical environment and collaborate to build a WSN [1]. These WSNs have a wide range of applications, including remote environmental monitoring, target tracking, infrastructure health monitoring, home and office automation and security, public security, event boundary identification, event detection, etc. [2] [3].

Through the use of WSNs, a large number of SNs with limited processing power, radio transceivers, storage, and battery life are placed in harsh and hostile environments. An SN is capable of measuring and manipulating itself, as well as communicating with other SNs [4].

Typically, the WSN consists of hundreds or thousands of SNs connected to the Base Station (BS), which acts as an interface between users and the network [5]. In addition, the user can navigate the WSN through the internet, as illustrated in figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1. An example of small WSN [6].

The growing popularity of this technology and the critical nature of the data transferred over the network necessitate the use of cryptographic methods to protect this data. WSN security techniques must address challenges such as confidentiality, authentication, integrity, and availability. Due to network constraints, providing good security must be accomplished with minimal energy consumption [7].

Asymmetric and symmetric techniques may be used to secure WSNs. While asymmetric key algorithms give greater security, they use more energy from the sensor nodes than symmetric key algorithms. The drawback of utilizing a symmetric key technique is the distribution of the keys. The downside of employing an asymmetric method is that it requires a lot of processing, which leads to wasting the sensor node's power. It is advised to use a hybrid technique that incorporates both asymmetric and symmetric algorithms. Hybridization's advantages can be applied to modern WSN security techniques [8].

To ease key distribution, one of the most hybrid techniques is to produce a random secret key for a symmetric key technique and then encrypt it with an asymmetric key technique using the recipient's public key. The secret message is encrypted using the symmetric key technique and the secret key [6].

Use of encryption and decryption techniques to ensure safe communication requires a high computational time and might significantly reduce the sensor's life. Additionally, due to the limited memory capacity and processing power available in WSNs, most standard cryptographic techniques are incompatible with them [9]. To ensure data secrecy in WSNs, three fundamental needs must be met: data authentication, data confidentiality, and data integrity. Encryption is commonly used on data in order to meet these criteria, resulting in an increase in energy costs. The energy cost includes the cost of transmission and encryption, which depends on the encryption algorithm implementation [9].

The energy limitation of a sensor node is a difficult constraint in WSNs. Researchers have concentrated their efforts on encryption algorithms that directly impact the energy cost of a WSN, either by analyzing current algorithms or proposing new energy-efficient algorithms [10].

1.2. Literature Survey

There are many works in the field of WSN cryptographic security. Some of the most recent works are:

In 2010, W. Ren and Z. Miao [11] proposed a Hybrid Algorithm (HA) using the Data Encryption Standard (DES) for data transmission due to its high efficiency in block encryption. Accordingly, Rivest Shamir Adleman (RSA) is used to encrypt the key of the DES due to its management pros in the key cipher. When sending encrypted data, the random number generator employs a one-time session key of the 64-bit DES. Accordingly, from the public key management center, the sender will have the public key. After that, use RSA to encrypt the session key. The ciphertext from DES encryption and the session key from RSA encryption are combined and sent out. Since using DES with RSA influences the security level, this algorithm is considered weak.

In 2013, M. Bafandehkar et al. [12] secured WSNs using two public key algorithms: Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) and RSA. They observed that ECC cryptography with a key size of 160 bits provides the same degree of security as RSA cryptography with a key size of 1024 bits. Thus, the ECC outperforms the RSA in terms of data transmission efficiency. As a result, the processing time complexity was lowered.

In 2015, R. Rizk and Y. Alkady [13] proposed a new security algorithm that depends on the Two-phase Hybrid Cryptography Algorithm (THCA), namely the private-key and public-key phases, to get high security with a short key. It provides three objectives of cryptography: confidentiality, integrity, and authentication. Furthermore, it combines the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and ECC to provide encryption. The XOR-DUAL RSA algorithm is used for authentication, and the Message Digest 5 (MD5) algorithm is used for integrity. The findings indicate that the proposed algorithm outperforms the competition in terms of the ciphertext size, computation time, and energy consumption in WSN. Also, it is robust against different kinds of attacks in the case of image encryption.

In 2016, D. Bhole et al. [14] proposed a new security protocol that can be used for online transactions using both symmetric and asymmetric keys. It guarantees three cryptographic objectives: authentication, confidentiality, and integrity, obtained with the help of AES, ECC, XOR-Dual RSA, and MD5 algorithms. It uses ECC and AES for encryption, MD5 for integrity, and XOR Dual RSA for authentication. This new security protocol is designed to provide better security and integrity using both private-key and public-key techniques.

In 2016, M. Rajalakshmi et al. [15] developed an enhanced encryption technique to address the security and resource restrictions associated with WSNs. The article developed a new security technique called the Energy

Efficient Cryptographic Algorithm (EECA) for increased security. It provides three fundamental cryptographic objectives: integrity, authentication, and confidentiality. Any data that is encrypted or decrypted requires two secure keys. The EECA algorithm's result indicates that it is more efficient than other algorithms in terms of processing time. The simulation results indicate that the proposed encryption technique has lower runtime and memory requirements than the various algorithms used in WSN.

In 2017, A. Pandey and U. Kumar [16] published an article titled "An improved AES cryptosystem based genetic method on S-box, with 256 key sizes and 14 rounds". The Improved AES (IAES) algorithm utilizes an adjusted S Box with a 256-bit key size through a Genetic Algorithm (GA). The IAES algorithm takes advantage of GA in the S-box to conduct various pipelined operations such as substitution, column mixing, row shifting, and adding around keys in AES rounds. The IAES and standard AES algorithms were constructed using the MATLAB simulator. Numerous comparative parameters, such as encryption and decryption times, have been computed. They discovered that the high degree of system integration, together with the high speed and throughput of IAES encryption, made it an attractive option for application usage.

In 2017, S. Prakash and A. Rajput [17] proposed an improved algorithm that included the benefits of both the ECC and AES algorithms. Their proposed algorithm was less complex than ECC. The hybrid algorithm uses ECC exclusively for key generation and AES exclusively for data encryption and decryption. They demonstrated that their proposed algorithm is more secure than AES by resolving AES's key sharing issue.

In 2018, K. Abdullah et al. [18] proposed a Hybrid Cryptography Algorithm (HCA) for WSN. The algorithm uses both symmetric and asymmetric keys, merging AES, RSA, and LZW compression. AES is a fast

symmetric-key algorithm that encrypts the first stage of plaintext. The second stage of the plaintext is encrypted using RSA to give the algorithm more protection and robustness. The LZW compression then follows the process. The reverse process follows the reversed algorithm steps, where the recipient initially follows the decompression step and decryption steps.

In 2019, S. Mohammed [19] proposed developing a hybrid security system called Multiple Elliptic Curve Cryptography–Blowfish (MECC-Blowfish), which combines two low-power encryption algorithms: asymmetric ECC and the symmetric Blowfish algorithm. Various keys are created utilizing three different models of the proposed MECC: a two-set key generator, a three-set key generator, and a four-set key generator. The MECC generates keys using a combination of multiple ECC techniques. Finally, the Diehard test was used to determine the unpredictability of the keys produced by the proposed MECC algorithm.

In 2019, A. Tripathy et al. [20] designed a hybrid cryptosystem to manage security in WSNs in order to eliminate memory and computational cost. First, a shared key is exchanged between nodes using ECC, a public key technique. The Rivest Cipher 4 (RC4) symmetric key technique is used to encrypt and decrypt data. Numerous performance metrics are calculated, such as the time required for encryption and decryption and the amount of memory required to store ciphertext data. In comparison to the standard techniques, the proposed model encrypts data faster and requires less memory for key storage.

In 2020, Pooja and R. Chauhan [21] developed a new cryptographic protocol using both symmetric and asymmetric keys. Asymmetric methods provide simpler key management, while symmetric methods provide a higher level of security. AES, DES, and m-RSA are used in different algorithm stages to achieve both symmetric and asymmetric benefits. AES

is used in stage 1, DES is used in stage 2, and m-RSA is used in the last stage. Accordingly, all stages are executed in parallel. In terms of execution, after comparing the present techniques with the proposed algorithm, we will find that the proposed algorithm produces a better outcome than the existing algorithms.

In 2020, O. Ebadati et al. [22] proposed a novel hybrid encryption algorithm for monitoring energy transmission lines and enhancing the security of WSNs that was developed to enhance power consumption. The proposed hybrid encryption algorithm ensures data transmission is secure and timely in WSNs used to monitor transmission pipelines. The proposed algorithm adheres to three cryptographic principles: confidentiality, integrity, and authentication. Elliptic curve Diffie Hellman (ECDH), Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA), and RSA are used to provide both confidentiality and authentication, and SHA-256 hashing is used to provide integrity.

In this thesis, three hybrid cryptographic algorithms have been proposed to provide a high-security level with low power consumption.

1.3. Problems Statement

This thesis discusses the most recently observed WSNs' problems. The first problem is that the data transmission in WSNs is vulnerable to attacks. The second problem is that traditional security algorithms consume a lot of energy during execution.

1.4. Aim of the Work

This thesis aims to propose secure and efficient cryptographic algorithms for WSNs that provide three objectives of cryptography: confidentiality, authentication, and integrity. In addition, the algorithms must have a good

tradeoff between high security and low power consumption to extend the WSN life while maintaining good protection.

The proposed algorithms must achieve the thesis's objectives. These objectives are accomplished by enhancing the security of WSNs through the construction of efficient algorithms that ensure robust data secrecy.

1.5. Thesis Contributions

This thesis makes several important contributions, which are discussed in detail below.

- For the first time in WSNs, the Lempel Ziv 4 (LZ4) lossless compression algorithm is used. It is applied before data encryption to reduce the plaintext size. Sending less data leads to less power consumption. Furthermore, it is proved that using LZ4 improves the ciphertext randomness, leading to high security.
- Merging both Blowfish and RC4 algorithms into one hybrid algorithm reduces encryption and decryption times while maintaining good security. Reducing computational time leads to less power consumption.
- Merging Blowfish, RC4, and AES algorithms into one hybrid algorithm reduces computational time. In addition, it provides excellent results in randomness tests, which means it achieves high security with less power consumption.

1.6. Thesis Outlines

This thesis was organized into five chapters, as follows:

Chapter One presents an introduction to the research. This chapter also explains the related works and highlights the problems statement of the work. In addition, it demonstrated the aim and objectives of this thesis.

Chapter Two offers a theoretical background related to WSNs, the security of WSNs, symmetric and asymmetric keys techniques, hashing algorithms, and compression algorithms. In addition, the randomness tests and the Raspberry Pi as a node are explained.

Chapter Three explains the proposed algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) with their codes and flowcharts.

Chapter Four shows the results and discussions of the proposed algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) in terms of ciphertext size, encryption time, decryption time, throughput, Diehard tests, and the benefits of using the LZ4 compression algorithm.

Chapter Five includes the conclusions and future works.

CHAPTER TWO

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Introduction

Protecting WSN data requires a high-security system that is low-power consumption and fast enough to fit within the constraints of these networks, which is a significant challenge. This thesis aims to develop hybrid security algorithms using both symmetric and asymmetric key techniques. The asymmetric key algorithm is used for key distribution and the symmetric key algorithms for data encryption, followed by a hashing algorithm to get integrity. In addition, a compression algorithm is used to reduce the ciphertext size. The proposed algorithms must be very secure and consume less energy and time in order to match the requirements and limitations of WSNs.

In this chapter, all the necessary algorithms and techniques for the proposed algorithms are explained well, such as the symmetric and asymmetric keys techniques, hashing algorithms, and compression algorithms. In addition, the randomness tests and the Raspberry Pi as a node will be explained in detail according to the corresponding references.

2.2. The Benefits of WSN Security

Numerous applications rely on sensor networks based on distributed wireless technologies. Due to resource constraints, some WSN applications operate without security, resulting in a deterioration in Quality of Service (QoS). A WSN connects a massive number of wireless sensors through Radio Frequency (RF) communication links. The quality of a node's operation in a WSN application is determined by its ability to comprehend, gather, and distribute information in the network. Energy consumption is a critical challenge since sensors are often rather small [23].

Additionally, wireless sensors have limited memory and the ability to function effectively because of the batteries' limited power [24]. Numerous Denial of Service (DoS) attacks are capable of causing damage to a network or node. If an attacked node continues to share information or ideas with its neighbors, resulting in the node losing all of its power, the node is declared dead in the worst-case scenario [25].

2.2.1. Security Objectives

A WSN's security needs may be classified into the following [26] [27]:

- **Confidentiality:** Ensure that the content of the messages is accessible only to approved sensor nodes.
- **Authentication:** Ensure that the data has originated from the specified source.
- **Integrity:** Ensure that any data received has not been altered during transmission by unauthorized parties.
- **Availability:** Ensure that the WSN or single-node services are always available.
- **Freshness:** Ensure that none of the previous data has been repeated.

2.2.2. Attacks and Attackers

An attack may be an attempt to gain unauthorized access to a service or information, or an endeavor to compromise a system's confidentiality, integrity, authentication, or availability. Attackers or intruders initiate the attacks. WSN adversary attacks include two types as following [28]:

- **Passive:** A person or other entity that only analyzes the communication channel and thus threatens data confidentiality.

- **Active:** Attempt to add, remove, or modify transmissions on the channel in a way that threatens confidentiality, authentication, or integrity.

2.3. Lightweight Cryptography (LWC) for WSN

The term "lightweight cryptography" refers to a collection of cryptographic symmetric and asymmetric algorithms that have been developed to offer appropriate security in systems that face special constraints in terms of operating environments and power capabilities, such as WSNs. In cryptography, lightweight may be performed on both the software and hardware levels, with energy consumption and chip size on the hardware level. In addition, RAM complexity and code size are classified as software levels. They are all used to evaluate the degree of optimization achieved by using LWC. The cryptographer's view is that both software and hardware implementations are optimized. Taking into account the fact that what is lightweight for the software implementation may not be lightweight for the hardware implementation, and vice versa [29].

To provide good protection against malicious attacks, traditional cryptographic techniques require big keys and several rounds. The issue with utilizing traditional cryptographic techniques to secure WSN-systems is that they waste a lot of power and need an area full of silicon. Thus, WSNs need suitable security techniques that are low-power, low-silicon, and high-performance. However, meeting all three needs in a single design is unachievable since only two of the three requirements can be met in a design that meets the lightweight objectives. Thus, designing a lightweight cryptographic technique is crucial since the cryptographer must consider three tradeoffs (security-cost, security-performance, and performance-cost) [30]. See figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1. Tradeoffs in the design of lightweight cryptographic algorithms [31].

There are two primary kinds of cryptographic techniques used to ensure the confidentiality of data [32] [33]. The two kinds are symmetric-key and asymmetric-key techniques. Both techniques have their own set of advantages and disadvantages.

In addition, to ensure data integrity, hashing is used, which is one of the cryptographic techniques. It produces a fixed-length and unique signature for a message. Secure Hashing Algorithms (SHA1, SHA2, and SHA256) and MD5 are widely used hashing algorithms [34].

2.4. Symmetric-key Techniques

Symmetric encryption techniques encrypt and decrypt data using the same unique key. There are two types of symmetric-key techniques. The first type is the stream cipher, which is an encryption technique that works byte by byte or bit by bit to transform plaintext into ciphertext, such as RC4, Trivium, and Turing. The second type is block ciphers, where each algorithm encrypts and decrypts a certain amount of data as a block and a specific key size, such as DES, Blowfish, and AES [35]. Only English alphabets, special symbols, and numerical values will be accepted as plaintext by such algorithms [35]. As a result, the output (ciphertext) will be a document composed of special

characters, alphabets, or numbers, or a combination of all three. The following is a list of the components of symmetric encryption [36]:

- **Plaintext:** This is the original data that the sender sends to a specific recipient. The data will be used to feed the encryption algorithm.
- **Encryption Algorithm:** This is a set of procedures that are run in plaintext with the help of a secret key to generate the ciphertext.
- **Secret Key:** The value that is combined with the plaintext to convert it to ciphertext. It is unrelated to plaintext.
- **Ciphertext:** This is the encrypted version of the original plaintext. It will be diametrically opposed to plaintext.
- **Decryption Algorithm:** Is a collection of operations that are applied to ciphertext with the aid of a secret key in order to recover the original plaintext.

The symmetric encryption process explanation is illustrated in figure 2.2. In addition, there are many advantages and disadvantages of symmetric-key cryptography that are clarified below [37] [38].

Figure 2.2. The symmetric encryption process explanation [35].

2.4.1. Advantages of Symmetric-key Techniques

- Symmetric-key ciphers may be designed to achieve high data throughput rates. Certain hardware implementations are capable of encrypting hundreds of gigabytes per second, whereas software versions may achieve throughput rates of a few megabytes per second.
- Symmetric-key ciphers use relatively short keys.
- Symmetric-key ciphers may be readily used as objectives to construct many cryptographic processes, such as computationally efficient digital signature techniques, Pseudo Random Number Generators (PNG), and hashing functions.
- The symmetric-key ciphers may be compiled to provide stronger ciphers. Uncomplicated transformations that are very easy to evaluate but have a low strength might be utilized to construct powerful products of ciphers.

2.4.2. Disadvantages of Symmetric-key Techniques

- When two parties communicate, the key must be kept secret on both sides.
- Because a big network has several key pairs, these keys must be maintained appropriately. As a result, managing the effective key requires the use of unconditionally trusted Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures (TTPs).
- To perform appropriate cryptography, it must regularly update the key, most likely for each single communication session.
- Digital signature techniques, which evolved from symmetric-key encryption, often demand the use of TTPs or a high key size for the purpose of public verification.

2.4.3. RC4 Algorithm

RC4 is one of the most widely used stream cipher encryption algorithms in the world today. Ron Rivest created this algorithm [39]. Additionally, the RC4 algorithm always introduces a table encoding data using a variable-length key of between 1 and 256 bits. RC4 is a two-step process. The first step is the primary setup, followed by the encryption step [40]. The primary setup step is the most difficult since it involves generating the encryption key variable from the base key, which is composed of two components: a scheduling algorithm for the keys and a pseudo-random number generation algorithm. Once these keys are generated, they are sent to the second step, where they are utilized to generate the encrypted message by XORing the key and the plaintext [41]. The RC4 algorithm's flowchart is illustrated in figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3. RC4 algorithm's flowchart [42].

2.4.4. Blowfish Algorithm

B. Schneier, one of the world's foremost cryptologists, invented the Blowfish algorithm and made it publicly accessible. Blowfish is a 64-bit block cipher with a variable-length key. The algorithm was introduced in 1993 and has remained uncrackable to date. Due to its tiny size, it may be optimized for hardware applications [43].

The algorithm is demonstrated in Figure 2.4. It is divided into two sections: a key expansion section and a data encryption section. A key with a maximum length of 448 bits is expanded into many sub-key arrays totaling 4168 bytes. Typically, encryption of data happens over a 16-round network. Each round consists of a permutation based on the key and a replacement based on the key and data. All operations on 32-bit words are XORs and additions. The only additional operations performed every round are four indexed array data lookups [44].

Figure 2.4. Basic Structure of Blowfish [44].

2.4.5. AES Algorithm

The AES is a symmetric block cipher algorithm that is widely used in cryptography. When data is encrypted using the AES algorithm, hackers have an extremely difficult time recovering the original data. The AES algorithm supports three key sizes: 128, 192, and 256 bits. However, the message block size is set at 128 bits [45].

AES is based on the substitution-permutation concept. The AES algorithm is composed of several rounds, which depend on the key length. Thus, AES with a key length of 128 bits has ten rounds, AES with a key length of 192 bits has twelve rounds, and AES with a key length of 256 bits has fourteen rounds. Each round is composed of the following procedures: add round key, sub bytes, shift rows, and mix columns [46]. Figure 2.5 shows the basic structure of AES.

Figure 2.5. Basic Structure of AES [45].

2.4.6. Cipher Modes

The block cipher mode is used to encrypt plaintext that exceeds the size of a single block. Block cipher modes are used for encryption and authentication [47].

In this thesis, Cipher Block Chaining (CBC) Mode is used to encrypt data. The mechanism of CBC is that the first block of plaintext must be XORed with the initial vector and then ciphered using the key. The next block is XORed with the prior one, and the result is ciphered using the key. The initial vector is randomly generated and is utilized for both encryption and decryption. This mode is used for ciphering and authentication [47]. Figures 2.6 and 2.7 show CBC encryption and decryption flowcharts, respectively.

Figure 2.6. CBC mode encryption flowchart [48].

Figure 2.7. CBC mode decryption flowchart [48].

2.5. Asymmetric-key Techniques

In 1976, W. Diffie and M. Hellman invented asymmetric key cryptography [49]. It encrypts and decrypts data using two keys: public and private keys. Two keys are mathematically connected. Due to the significant burden associated with asymmetric key cryptography in terms of memory computation and power consumption, it is typically not preferred in WSN [50].

While the public key can be broadcast to all nodes, the private key must be kept secret. To connect public and private keys, we apply mathematical logic. While the public key was broadcast to all nodes, a hacker could not recover the private key just by using the public key. Assume that a message was encrypted using the public key that is known. We need a private key to decrypt the ciphertext. Generally, we prefer to encrypt using our private key and decrypt with our public key. Figure 2.8 illustrates the public-key cryptosystem in WSNs.

Figure 2.8. The public-key cryptosystem in WSNs [51].

We must simplify this technique in order to apply it in a WSN environment. The network deployer might take the place of the trusted third party. It can deploy nodes using a private-public key pair. Each node in

the network has the ability to broadcast its public key to its neighbors if required in order to encrypt messages. However, a trustworthy certificate authority that provides proper certificates is required to authenticate the public key [51].

Three different families have been formed for practical use among all public-key algorithms. These systems' security is dependent on difficult mathematical problems: RSA, discrete logarithm, and ECC.

This thesis used the ECDH algorithm, which is an algorithm from the ECC family based on the D. Hellman scheme for key exchange rather than an encryption algorithm. ECDH specifies the methods of generating and exchanging keys between two parties. Each chosen curve is used on its standard's prime field. From the curve, a random point P is chosen.

According to [52], ECDH is the best secure asymmetric-key algorithm. Accordingly, the mathematical problem of ECDH is solved by fully exponential time whether other public-key systems are solved by sub-exponential time. ECDH needs a shorter key than other algorithms, which refers to less memory size. It lets the communication nodes handling more requests with fewer dropped packets.

Overall an elliptic curve has the form of

$$y^2 = x^3 + ax + b \quad (2.1)$$

where a and b are defined parameters. Within ECC, we pick a point on the curve (G - the generator) and perform our operations with the modulus of p . The final parameters are η - the subgroup size - and h - the cofactor. There are many different elliptic curve standards, including secp256k1, secp192r1, p224, p256, and p384.

Figure 2.9 show the used procedure to exchange keys between Alice and Bob using the ECDH algorithm, which is [53]:

- Bob will generate a public and private keys by taking a point on the curve G . The private key is a random number d_B , and Bob's public key Q_B will be:

$$Q_B = d_B \times G \quad (2.2)$$

- Alice will do the same and generate her public key Q_A from her private key d_A :

$$Q_A = d_A \times G \quad (2.3)$$

- They then exchange their public keys. Alice will then use Bob's public key and her private key to calculate:

$$\text{Alice Shared key} = d_A \times Q_B \quad (2.4)$$

This will be the same as:

$$\text{Alice Shared key} = d_A \times d_B \times G \quad (2.5)$$

- Bob will then use Alice's public key and his private key to calculate:

$$\text{Bob Shared key} = d_B \times Q_A \quad (2.6)$$

This will be the same as:

$$\text{Bob Shared key} = d_B \times d_A \times G \quad (2.7)$$

- And the keys will thus match.

Figure 2.9. The procedure of the ECDH algorithm [53].

2.6. Hashing Functions

A Cryptographic Hash Function (CHF) is a mathematical procedure that converts data of any size (commonly referred to as the "message") to a fixed-size bit array (the "hash value", "hash", or "message digest"). It is a one-way function, which means that inverting or reversing the calculation is almost impossible [54]. Typically, the only ways to detect a message that generates a specific hash are to do a brute-force search of possible inputs to see whether they generate a match or utilize a rainbow table of matched hashes. CHF is a fundamental component of modern cryptography.

A cryptographic hash function must be deterministic, which means that it must always produce the same hash for the same message. Additionally, it should possess the following characteristics:

- Calculating the hash value of any message is simple.

- It is impossible to produce a message containing a specific hash value (i.e., reverse the process that generated the given hash value).
- It is impossible to detect two different messages that have the same hash value.
- A minor modification to a message should result in a significant change to the hash value, such that the new hash value looks unrelated to the previous hash value [55].

Cryptographic hash functions have a wide variety of applications in information security, most notably digital signatures, Message Authentication Codes (MACs), and other types of authentication. They may also be used as standard hash functions to index data in hash tables, fingerprinting, detecting duplicate data or uniquely identifying files, and checksums to detect data corruption caused by human error.

Indeed, cryptographic hash values are sometimes referred to as digital fingerprints, checksums, or just hash values in information-security contexts, despite all of these names referring to more generic functions with very different features and objectives. The most commonly used hashing algorithms are SHA1, SHA2, SHA256, and MD5.

This thesis used the MD5 hashing algorithm, which is one of the message digest algorithms proposed by Professor Ronald Rivest in 1991 as a safer replacement to MD4 [56].

- Input: arbitrary-length message.
- Output: A hash code of 128 bits.

The input message is divided into 512-bit segments (sixteen 32-bit words). If the message's length is not an integer multiple of 512-bit blocks, it is padded to be divisible by 512.

MD5 is composed of 64 operations, which are organized into four rounds of 16 operations each. F is a non-linear function; each round uses a different function. M_i is a 32-bit block of the message's input data, and K_i is a 32-bit constant that is different for each operation. s represents a left bit rotation [57]. The primary MD5 algorithm operates on a 128-bit state, which is split into four 32-bit words indicated by the letters A , B , C , and D . These are initially set to a set of predefined constants.

$$A = 0x67452301$$

$$B = 0xEFCDAB89$$

$$C = 0x98BADCFE$$

$$D = 0x10325376$$

The main algorithm then modifies the state using each 512-bit message block in turn. A message block is processed in four identical steps, referred to as rounds; each round consists of sixteen similar operations based on a non-linear function F , modular addition, and left rotation. Figure 2.10 illustrates a single operation within a round. There are four possible functions F ; each round uses a different one:

$$F(B,C,D)=(B \text{ AND } C) \text{ OR } (\text{NOT } B \text{ AND } D)$$

$$G(B,C,D)= (B \text{ AND } D) \text{ OR } (C \text{ AND NOT } D)$$

$$H(B,C,D)= B \text{ XOR } C \text{ XOR } D$$

$$I(B,C,D)= C \text{ XOR } (B \text{ OR NOT } D)$$

The resulting value is referred to as a hash, a fingerprint, or a message digest [34].

Figure 2.10. A single operation within a round of MD5 [57].

2.7. Compression Algorithms

Compression of data refers to the process of lowering the amount of space required to store data or the amount of time required to transmit data. By deleting redundant data, the amount of data is decreased. Data compression aims to represent a source in digital form using the fewest feasible bits while still fulfilling the minimal requirements for reconstructing the original.

Data compression can be lossless only if the original data can be exactly reconstructed from the compressed form. This kind of lossless technique is employed when the original data from a source is critical and we cannot afford to lose any information. Medical pictures, text and photos maintained for legal reasons, and some computer executable files are all examples of such source material [58].

Data compression ratio is defined as the ratio between the uncompressed size and compressed size [59]:

$$\text{compression ratio} = \frac{\text{uncompressed size}}{\text{compressed size}} \quad (2.8)$$

Another family of compression techniques is called lossy because they permanently eliminate segments of data and can be reconstructed only as an

approximation of the original material. Approximate reconstruction is sometimes preferable since it results in more effective compression. However, it often necessitates balancing visual quality and computational complexity. Due to the way human visual and hearing systems function, data such as multimedia pictures, videos, and audio are more readily compressed using lossy compression algorithms. Some of the lossy compression commonly used algorithms are Joint Photographic Experts Group (JPEG), Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG), and MPEG audio Layer-3 (MP3).

While lossy algorithms are more effective than lossless algorithms, they are only useful for audio, pictures, and video when some loss is acceptable.

The debate over which technique is superior, "lossless" or "lossy", is meaningless since each has its own set of applications, with lossless techniques being superior in certain cases and lossy techniques being superior in others [59].

Nowadays, there are several lossless compression techniques, the majority of which are based on probability, dictionaries, and entropy. In other words, they all attempt to compress data by using the presence of the same character or string. There are many types of lossless compression, such as Huffman Coding, Shannon-Fano Coding, Run Length Encoding, and the Lempel-Ziv scheme, which is separated into two families: those derived from LZ77 (LZ77, LZ4, LZSS, LZH, and LZB) and those derived from LZ78 (LZ78, LZW, and LZFG) [60].

This thesis used the LZ4 algorithm due to its simplicity, speed, and good compression ratio. LZ4 is not an algorithm in the conventional sense. LZ4 specifies just an output data format like LZ77 [60]. This enables the creation of several variants of compression techniques (with varying speeds and compression ratios) as well as the decompression of the LZ4 file format using a single tool, regardless of the compression algorithm employed.

However, the creator of LZ4 produced a reference implementation in the C programming language, which has been translated into a large number of other programming languages. To ensure optimal performance, the LZ4 code contains several optimizations for different Central Processing Unit (CPU) architectures.

LZ4 and LZ77 are both asymmetric compression algorithms in which decompression is much simpler and faster than compression. The mechanism of decompression is extremely similar to that of LZ77. It is based on the decoded part's literals being copied.

LZ4 utilizes a dictionary-matching step like LZ77. But unlike other popular compression algorithms, it does not combine it with an entropy coding step [61].

The LZ4 algorithm stores data in the form of sequences; each sequence starts with a one-byte token split into two four-bit fields. The first field specifies how many literal bytes should be copied to the output. The second field specifies the number of bytes to copy from the output buffer that has already been decoded (with 0 representing the minimum match length of 4 bytes). A value of 15 in any of the bitfields indicates that the length has been increased and an additional byte of data is to be added. A value of 255 in these additional bytes implies the addition of another byte. As a result, arbitrary lengths are represented by a series of extra bytes containing the value 255. The string of literals follows the token and any additional bytes required to indicate the length of the string. This is followed by an offset specifying the position in the output buffer from which to begin copying. The additional bytes (if any) associated with the match-length are appended at the end of the sequence [60].

Compression can be carried out in a stream or in blocks. Compression ratios can be increased by putting more effort into finding the optimal matches. This results in reduced output size and faster decompression [62].

2.8. Randomness Test

Random sequences and random integers are required for ciphering to work. Numerous ciphering techniques are based on the use of random values. The ciphertext of the higher random number provides a higher level of security. Statistical tests are used to determine randomness. As a result, evaluating the security of ciphering algorithms is highly dependent on statistical random tests [63] [64].

Numerous practical randomness metrics have been used to determine the randomness of a binary sequence. The randomness measurements are based on statistical tests, transforms, complexity, or a combination of them. The most commonly used test introduced by Marsaglia is called the Diehard Test [65].

This thesis used the Diehard test, which is a set of statistical tests used to evaluate the random number generator's quality. They were created over many years by George Marsaglia and originally published in 1995 [63]. The tests for Diehard are:

- **Birthday Spacings Test:** Selects m birthdays in a year of n days and lists the spacings between them. It then determines a best-fit line and determines the deviation from the expected distribution function. This deviation determines the quality of this test.
- **Overlapping 5-Permutation Test:** Analyzes a sequence of one million randomly generated integers. It then calculates the ordering of the five numbers in each group of five consecutive integers (in ascending or descending order). It then counts the number of each of

the 120 (5!) possible configurations and calculates the variance between the expected plot of these values and the observed plot.

- **Binary Rank Test:** 40,000 31x31 matrices are constructed from 31 different integers and their ranks are determined. Following that, the count of matrices with ranks of 28, 29, 30, and 31 is determined and compared to the expected values. This is repeated 100,000 times for 6x8 matrices over 25 iterations, with each iteration providing a p -value.
- **Bitstream Test:** Counts the number of 20-bit words that are missing from a 2^{21} -bit bitstream. This should be distributed normally.
- **Overlapping Pairs Sparse Occupancy (OPSO):** Similar to the bitstream test, but utilizes 10-bit letter and 2-letter words and extracts different bits from each word.
- **Overlapping Quadruples Sparse Occupancy (OQSO):** Similar to OPSO, but use 5-bit letter and 4-letter words. The variation from the mean value determines the p -value.
- **Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Test:** Similar to the previous three, but it uses 5-bit letters and 4-letter words.
- **Count the 1's Test:** By using a 256,000 sample, this test calculates how many times 8-bit letter and 5-letter words appear and calculates variance. There are two types of these tests: one for a stream of bytes and the other for specific bytes.
- **Parking Lot Test:** Park cars randomly in a square with 100 sides, and do not park the car if an accident happens. Carry out this procedure for $n = 12,000$ cars and compare the number of successfully parked cars to the expected number.

- **Minimum Distance Test:** Selects $n = 8,000$ random points in a square and then calculates the distance between all pairs of points. These distances should be distributed exponentially. The variation from the expected value is used to calculate the P -value.
- **Three-Dimensional (3D) Spheres Test:** 4000 random points are chosen and arranged into a 1000×1000 cube. A sphere large enough to just touch the nearest cube is present at each point's center. The smallest radius is determined, and the test is performed 20 times. These radii should be exponentially distributed, and the p -value will be calculated based on the distance between the observed and expected values.
- **Squeeze Test:** Using $k = 2^{31}$ as a starting point, multiply by floating point numbers in the range $[0, 1]$ until $k = 1$. This is performed 100,000 times, and the number of times it is less than or equal to 7 and greater than 47 is counted and compared to the expected exponential to obtain the p -value.
- **Overlapping Sums Test:** Add 100 consecutive integers, incrementing by one element at a time and storing each of the sums, which should have a normal distribution. The p -value is calculated by comparing the results to the normal distribution.
- **Runs Test:** Iterates through 10,000 values and identifies successive runs in which elements' values increase or decrease sequentially. After that, the matrix is compared to a well-known covariance matrix.
- **Craps Test:** Plays 200,000 games of craps in order to determine the number of throws required to terminate each game. The number of wins should closely match the normal distribution.

The Diehard produces groups of p -values that fall inside the interval $[0,1]$. As demonstrated in table 2.1, the interval is divided into three areas: safe, doubt, and failure.

Table 2.1. The Diehard Test's limits of safe, doubt, and failure areas.

areas	limits
safe area	$0.25 > p\text{-value} \leq 0.75$
doubt area	$0.1 > p\text{-value} \leq 0.25$ and $(0.75 > p\text{-value} \leq 0.9$
failure area	$0 > p\text{-value} \leq 0.1$ or $(0.9 > p\text{-value} \leq 1$

The p -values may fall into one of three areas (failure, doubt, and safe). When many p -values located in the failure area, it indicates a low level of randomness. On the other hand, the randomness will be higher if the p -values are closer to the safe area [66].

2.9. Raspberry Pi as a WSN Node

The Raspberry Pi is a tiny, powerful, low-cost computer board that is hackable and geared toward education. This credit card-sized computer is ideal for interacting with various devices due to its many ports and connections. Additionally, it has a CPU, graphics chip, and Random Access Memory (RAM) for program storage. One of the wonderful things about the Raspberry Pi is its flexibility; there is no single-use for it, which is important for WSNs' wide range of useful applications. The Raspberry Pi is an excellent candidate for the WSNs node [67]. However, its disadvantage is consuming more power than other types of nodes.

This thesis used the Raspberry Pi 4 Model B, the latest Raspberry Pi version. It is important to note that the performance of the new Raspberry Pi 4 Model B is equivalent to that of an entry-level x86 computer.

CHAPTER THREE

THE PROPOSED HYBRID ALGORITHMS

3.1. Introduction

This thesis proposes three lightweight hybrid cryptographic algorithms to give the best tradeoff between high security and processing time reduction. In this chapter, three proposed hybrid algorithms are presented, which are the LZ4–ECDH–Blowfish–MD5 (LEBM) algorithm, the LZ4–ECDH–Blowfish–RC4–MD5 (LEBRM) algorithm, and the LZ4–ECDH–Blowfish–RC4–MD5 (LEBRAM) algorithm. In addition, the procedure and flowchart of each proposed algorithm are illustrated in a suitable manner.

3.2. LEBM Hybrid Algorithm

The proposed algorithm includes a scheme that compresses data and then merges both private-key and public-key techniques with hashing to provide confidentiality, authentication, and integrity. The encryption and decryption processes are well explained below.

3.2.1. The LEBM Encryption Process

In encryption, the plaintext is compressed using LZ4 compression, and then the compressed data is split into n blocks symbolized as bi , where i is the block counter. Every block consists of 64 bits. If n is not an integer, the last block is padded with null as a 64-bit block. Thus, the encryption process is split into three steps:

- i. The plaintext is compressed using the LZ4 algorithm to reduce its size and, subsequently, the encryption and decryption times since it is almost the fastest lossless compression algorithm for texts. It then divides the compressed data into 64-bit blocks.

- ii. The compressed blocks are encrypted using the Blowfish algorithm with a 64-bit block length, and the block series is encoded in CBC mode. In CBC mode, each plaintext block is XORed with the preceding ciphertext block before being encrypted. Continuously, until each ciphertext block depends on all plaintext blocks processed up to that point. An initialization vector must be used in the first block to make each message unique. On the other hand, the ECDH algorithm is used for key exchange. It is the most secure asymmetric-key algorithm. Accordingly, the mathematical problem of ECDH is solved by fully exponential time, while other public-key systems are solved by sub-exponential time. ECDH needs a shorter key than other algorithms, which refers to less memory size. It lets the communication nodes handle more requests with fewer dropped packets. Since ECDH needs more power than the private-key algorithms, using the Blowfish algorithm decreases power consumption and improves system performance. Using Blowfish with ECDH can speed up the encryption and decryption process and save power.
- iii. MD5 is applied to the ciphertext and the sender's public key. Then MD5 hashing code, the sender's public key, and the Blowfish ciphertext are merged and sent to the receiver, as demonstrated in figure 3.1. MD5 has the best performance compared with other hashing functions.

Figure 3.1. The LEBM encryption flowchart.

3.2.2. The LEBM Decryption Process

Decryption follows the reversing steps:

- i. Split the receiving block into three blocks (MD5 hashing, sender public key, and Blowfish ciphertext). Then take the MD5 hashing code to (sender public key + Blowfish ciphertext) and compare it with

the received MD5 hash code. If they are equal, then the message is not modified; else, it is altered and needs to be discarded.

- ii. Exchange the key with the sender using the ECDH algorithm to transfer keys through an insecure channel. Then decrypt the ciphertext with Blowfish by splitting the ciphertext into n blocks symbolized as bi , where i is the block counter. Every block consisted of 64 bits decrypted using Blowfish with CBC mode.
- iii. Decompress the previous step's result using LZ4 decompression, so the receiver gets the plaintext. Figure 3.2 shows the LEBM decryption process.

Figure 3.2. The LEBM decryption flowchart.

3.3. LEBRM Hybrid Algorithm

The proposed algorithm compresses data and then uses two symmetric techniques and one asymmetric technique with hashing to provide confidentiality, authentication, and integrity. The encryption and decryption processes are clarified below.

3.3.1. The LEBRM Encryption Process

The Blowfish encryption is a block cipher, so the data must be a multiple of eight bytes. Otherwise, it must be padded, while RC4 is a stream cipher that does not need padding. The encryption process may be summarized into four steps:

- i. The plaintext is compressed using the LZ4 algorithm to decrease its size, thus reducing the time required for encryption and decryption since it is almost the fastest lossless text compression algorithm. The compressed data is then divided into two blocks. To avoid padding, which increases ciphertext size, the first block is half of the compressed data minus the same number modulus 8. The second block contains the rest of the compressed data.
- ii. The ECDH method is used for key exchange. It is the most secure and fastest asymmetric-key algorithm. ECDH requires a smaller key than other algorithms, which results in less memory space. It enables communication nodes to handle more requests with fewer packet drops. Due to the fact that ECDH consumes more power than private-key methods, employing the Blowfish and RC4 algorithms reduces power consumption and enhances system performance. By combining Blowfish, RC4, and ECDH, we can speed up the encryption and decryption processes with saving power.

- iii. The first block is divided into 8-byte blocks and encrypted using Blowfish. Each 8-byte block is encrypted using the Blowfish algorithm, and the block series is encoded using the CBC mode. The second block is encrypted using the RC4 algorithm.
- iv. MD5 is applied to the ciphertexts and the sender's public key. Then the MD5 hashing code, the sender's public key, the Blowfish ciphertext, and the RC4 ciphertext are combined and sent to the receiver as illustrated in figure 3.3. MD5 offers the greatest performance compared to other hashing algorithms.

3.3.2. The LEBRM Decryption Process

Decryption follows the reversing steps of the encryption process, as shown in figure 3.4.

3.4. LEBRAM Hybrid Algorithm

The proposed algorithm compresses data, uses three symmetric algorithms and one asymmetric algorithm, and then hashes ciphertexts to provide confidentiality, authentication, and integrity. The encryption and decryption processes are demonstrated below.

3.4.1. The LEBRAM Encryption Process

The Blowfish and AES encryptions are block ciphers, so the data must be a multiple of 8 bytes for the Blowfish and a multiple of 16 bytes for the AES. Otherwise, it must be padded, while RC4 is a stream cipher that does not need padding. The encryption process is split into four steps:

- i. The plaintext is compressed using the LZ4 algorithm to decrease its size, thus reducing the time required for encryption and decryption. Then The compressed data is divided into three blocks. To avoid padding that increases ciphertext size, each of the first and third blocks

is one-third of the compressed data minus the same number modulus 16. At the same time, the second block contains the rest of the compressed data.

Figure 3.3. The LEBRM encryption flowchart.

Figure 3.4. The LEBRM decryption flowchart.

- ii. The ECDH method is used for key exchange. Since ECDH consumes more power than symmetric techniques, the Blowfish, RC4, and AES algorithms reduce power consumption and improve system performance. By merging Blowfish, RC4, AES, and ECDH, we can speed up the encryption and decryption processes while saving power.
- iii. The first and third blocks are divided into 16-byte blocks and encrypted using Blowfish and AES, respectively. The block series for both are encoded using the CBC mode. The second block is encrypted using the RC4 algorithm.
- iv. MD5 is applied to the ciphertexts and the sender's public key. Then the MD5 hashing code, the sender's public key, and the ciphertexts of Blowfish, RC4, and AES, respectively, are merged and sent to the receiver as shown in figure 3.5.

3.4.2. The LEBRAM Decryption Process

Decryption follows the reversing steps of the encryption process, as demonstrated in figure 3.6.

Figure 3.5. The LEBRAM encryption flowchart.

Figure 3.6. The LEBRAM decryption flowchart.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Introduction

The metrics used to evaluate the performance of the three proposed algorithms are the ciphertext size, encryption time, and decryption time, in addition to the throughput. In addition, the three proposed algorithms are compared with previous works, which are THCA [13], HA [11], and HCA [18]. All proposed algorithms were subjected to Diehard tests to compute the randomness of their ciphertexts, as more randomness in ciphertexts means a more secure algorithm. In addition, the benefits of using the LZ4 compression algorithm are presented. Finally, all experiments were applied using two computers, namely A and B, in addition to the Raspberry Pi. Tables 4.1 and 4.2 show the hardware and software specifications of the used computers.

Table 4.1. A comparison of the hardware specifications between the used computers.

comparison point	computer-A	computer-B	Raspberry Pi 4 Model B
manufacturing date	2014	2004	2019
processor	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-4510U CPU @ 2.00GHz (4 CPUs), ~2.60 GHz	Intel(R) Pentium(R) processor ~1.5 GHz	64-bit quad-core Cortex-A72 processor
RAM	8.00 GB	512 MB	2GB
Hard disk	1 TB HDD	40 GB HDD	32 GB external SD card

Table 4.2. A comparison of the software specifications between the used computers.

comparison point	computer-A	computer-B	Raspberry Pi 4 Model B
Operating system	windows 10 (64-bit)	windows XP (32-bit)	Raspbian
Python IDE	PyCharm version 2021.2.1	PyCharm version 4.5.5	Thonny version 3.3.10
Python version	3.9.7	3.4.3	3.7.3

4.2. The Ciphertext Size

Table 4.3 and figure 4.1 show the ciphertext size in bytes of the proposed algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) compared with the previously presented algorithms THCA [13], HA [11], and HCA [18].

Table 4.3. A comparison of ciphertext sizes (bytes) between the proposed and previously presented algorithms.

Plaintext size (B)	HA [11]	THCA [13]	HCA [18]	LEBM	LEBRM	LEBRAM
609	602	641	648	529	528	528
25,615	25,610	25,647	25647	16937	16935	16935
35,080	35,070	35,112	35116	22969	22964	22964
61,386	61,369	61,418	61421	39321	39318	39318
184,162	184,143	184,194	184201	116113	116112	116112

It is demonstrated that the HCA [18] algorithm has the largest ciphertext size, while other algorithms give ciphertext sizes that are very similar in size to plaintext. In contrast, the proposed algorithms have the smallest ciphertext sizes due to the use of LZ4 compression. LEBM has a little bit more ciphertext size due to padding in the Blowfish block cipher, while it is overcome in LEBRM and LEBRAM due to removing the padding.

Figure 4.1. A comparison of ciphertext sizes (bytes) between the proposed and previously presented algorithms.

4.3. The Encryption Time

The encryption time indicates the time spent converting plaintext to ciphertext. Tables 4.4, 4.5, and 4.6, with the corresponding figures 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4, show a comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) using computer-A, computer-B, and the Raspberry Pi, respectively, with previously presented algorithms THCA [13], HA [11], and HCA [18] for various plaintext sizes. The tables include the average of ten runtimes.

Table 4.4. A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms.

Plaintext size (B)	HA [11]	THCA [13]	HCA [18]	computer-A		
				LEBM	LEBRM	LEBRAM
609	1,432	998	548	107.6	96.5	142.5
25,615	1490	1022	990	133.7	99.3	150.8
35,080	1,468	1,059	1,037	143.4	100.1	154.4
61,386	3019	3143	2345	168.8	107.1	160.3
184,162	4,970	3,814	3187	294.9	149.7	189.4

Figure 4.2. A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms.

The results show that all the proposed algorithms obtain less encryption time than previously presented algorithms when using computer-A. LEBRM has the least encryption time, and then LEBRAM. While LEBM has a little bit more encryption time when the plaintext is huge, such as 184,162 B.

Table 4.5. A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms.

Plaintext size (B)	HA [11]	THCA [13]	HCA [18]	computer-B		
				LEBM	LEBRM	LEBRAM
609	1,432	998	548	241.7	237.3	243.5
25,615	1490	1022	990	335.6	284	273.4
35,080	1,468	1,059	1,037	371.4	300.4	285.8
61,386	3019	3143	2345	463.8	348.5	317.8
184,162	4,970	3,814	3187	903.7	564.7	467.5

Figure 4.3. A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms.

The results demonstrated that all the proposed algorithms obtain less encryption time than previously presented algorithms when using computer-B. LEBRAM has the least encryption time, followed by LEBRM. In contrast, LEBM has more encryption time.

Table 4.6. A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms.

Plaintext size (B)	HA [11]	THCA [13]	HCA [18]	Raspberry Pi		
				LEBM	LEBRM	LEBRAM
609	1,432	998	548	165.1	164.5	166
25,615	1490	1022	990	218.4	191.4	188.8
35,080	1,468	1,059	1,037	246.3	200.2	194.8
61,386	3019	3143	2345	300.4	229.5	210.7
184,162	4,970	3,814	3187	566.4	368	303.1

Figure 4.4. A comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms.

The results show that all the proposed algorithms obtain less encryption time than previously presented algorithms when using the Raspberry Pi. LEBRAM has the least encryption time, followed by LEBRM. In contrast, LEBM has more encryption time.

4.4. The Decryption Time

The decryption time indicates the time spent converting ciphertext to plaintext. Tables 4.7, 4.8, and 4.9, with the corresponding figures 4.5, 4.6, and 4.7, show a comparison of encryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) using computer-A, computer-B, and the Raspberry Pi, respectively, with previously presented algorithms THCA [13], HA [11], and HCA [18] for various plaintext sizes. The tables include the average of ten runtimes.

The results show that all the proposed algorithms obtain less decryption time than previously presented algorithms when using computer-A. LEBRM

has the least decryption time, and then LEBM has less decryption time than LEBRAM, but only when the plaintext is huge, such as 184,162 B, it has a little bit more decryption time than LEBRAM. On the other hand, LEBRAM has the advantage of almost linear relationships, which means it is best when working with huge plaintexts.

Table 4.7. A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms.

Plaintext size (B)	HA [11]	THCA [13]	HCA [18]	Computer-A		
				LEBM	LEBRM	LEBRAM
609	756	562	221	91	71.7	143.4
25,615	821	713	636	115.3	85.6	149.4
35,080	953	824	762	126	92.6	151.2
61,386	864	891	795	153.3	105.7	159.1
184,162	1,075	907	856	290.6	181.1	190.5

Figure 4.5. A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms.

Table 4.8. A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms.

Plaintext size (B)	HA [11]	THCA [13]	HCA [18]	Computer-B		
				LEBM	LEBRM	LEBRAM
609	756	562	221	264.2	267.5	266.3
25,615	821	713	636	353.6	333.5	296.9
35,080	953	824	762	389.1	363.3	309.9
61,386	864	891	795	479.1	439.9	344.2
184,162	1,075	907	856	914.4	794.8	501

Figure 4.6. A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms.

The results demonstrated that LEBRAM has the least decryption time, followed by LEBRM. Both obtain less decryption time than previously presented algorithms when using computer-B. While when the plaintext is huge, such as 184,162 B, LEBM has a little bit more decryption time than THCA [13] and HCA [18].

Table 4.9. A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms.

Plaintext size (B)	HA [11]	THCA [13]	HCA [18]	the Raspberry Pi		
				LEBM	LEBRM	LEBRAM
609	756	562	221	172.2	171.7	173.5
25,615	821	713	636	225.1	219.7	197
35,080	953	824	762	250.3	235.4	204.4
61,386	864	891	795	305.4	289.9	223.9
184,162	1,075	907	856	575.2	518.2	319.5

Figure 4.7. A comparison of decryption time (ms) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms.

The results show that all the proposed algorithms obtain less decryption time than previously presented algorithms when using the Raspberry Pi. LEBRAM has the least decryption time, followed by LEBRM. In contrast, LEBM has a little bit more decryption time.

4.5. The Throughput

The throughput of an encryption scheme is calculated by using encryption time. It indicates the encryption speed. The encryption scheme's throughput is calculated as HCA [18].

$$\text{Throughput of encryption} = \frac{Tp \text{ (bytes)}}{Et \text{ (seconds)}} \quad (4.1)$$

Where Tp is the total plaintext (in bytes), and Et is the encryption time (s). Tables 4.10, 4.11, and 4.12, with the corresponding figures 4.8, 4.9, and 4.10, respectively, show the throughput of the three proposed algorithms. All tables and corresponding figures were applied in the same sequence using computers A, B, and the Raspberry Pi. All results in each table are compared with previous algorithms presented in THCA [13], HA [11], and HCA [18] for different plaintext sizes. In addition, the tables include the average of ten runtimes.

Table 4.10. A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms.

Plaintext size (B)	HA [11]	THCA [13]	HCA [18]	Computer-A		
				LEBM	LEBRM	LEBRAM
609	425	610	1111	5659.5	6310.5	4273.2
25,615	17191	25064	25874	191636.9	258074.6	169859.1
35,080	23897	33126	33828	244698.6	350435.7	227212
61,386	20333	19531	26177	363705.2	573364.4	382930.8
184,162	37055	48286	57785	624520.6	1229814.3	972385.2

Figure 4.8. A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using computer-A and previously presented algorithms.

The results show that all the proposed algorithms obtain much more throughput than previously presented algorithms when using computer-A. LEBRM has the most throughput, followed by LEBRAM. While LEBM has less throughput when the plaintext is huge, such as 184,162 B.

Table 4.11. A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms.

Plaintext size (B)	HA [11]	THCA [13]	HCA [18]	Computer-B		
				LEBM	LEBRM	LEBRAM
609	425	610	1111	2519.3	2566.2	2501
25,615	17191	25064	25874	76328.4	90203.1	93685.4
35,080	23897	33126	33828	94458.3	116786.2	122739.8
61,386	20333	19531	26177	132352.3	176158.3	193174.6
184,162	37055	48286	57785	203782.7	326114.4	393969.3

Figure 4.9. A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using computer-B and previously presented algorithms.

The results demonstrated that all the proposed algorithms obtain much more throughput than previously presented algorithms when using computer-B. LEBRAM has the most throughput, followed by LEBRM. In contrast, LEBM has less throughput.

Table 4.12. A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms.

Plaintext size (B)	HA [11]	THCA [13]	HCA [18]	Raspberry Pi		
				LEBM	LEBRM	LEBRAM
609	425	610	1111	3689.4	3703.1	3668
25,615	17191	25064	25874	117293.7	133810.7	135692.7
35,080	23897	33126	33828	142445.9	175225	180094.1
61,386	20333	19531	26177	204372.2	267465.7	291290
184,162	37055	48286	57785	325136.8	500378.1	607639.1

Figure 4.10. A comparison of throughput (bytes/s) between the proposed algorithms using the Raspberry Pi and previously presented algorithms.

The results show that all the proposed algorithms obtain much more throughput than previously presented algorithms when using the Raspberry Pi. LEBRAM has the most throughput, followed by LEBRM. In contrast, LEBM has less throughput.

4.6. The Diehard Tests

The Diehard test is used to measure the randomness of the security algorithms. It contains 222 p -values from 15 tests. The algorithm with fewer failure p -values has more randomness, leading to more security. Figures 4.11, 4.12, 4.13, and 4.14 show the p -value distributions over safe, doubt, and failure areas for plaintext, LEBM ciphertext, LEBRM ciphertext, and LEBRAM ciphertext, respectively. Practically, a file of more than 10 MB size must be used to have the most accurate results. A random readable text file of 24.8 MB size is used for plaintext, and it produces a ciphertext of 10.7 MB size for all proposed algorithms due to the use of LZ4 compression. Table 4.13 and figure 4.15 show a comparison between the proposed

algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) and the previously presented MECC algorithm [19].

The results show that LEBRAM has the best randomness because it has the least failure p -values. LEBM has the same failure p -values as LEBRAM but with less safe p -values. Followed by LEBRM, which has a little bit more failure p -values. In contrast, all the proposed algorithms are much better than the previously presented MECC algorithm [19].

Figure 4.11. p -values distribution for the plaintext.

Figure 4.12. p -values distribution for the LEBM.

Figure 4.13. p -values distribution for the LEBRM.

Figure 4.14. p -values distribution for the LEBRAM.

Table 4.13. A comparison of Diehard results between the proposed algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) and the previously presented MECC algorithm [19].

algorithms	safe	doubt	failure
LEBM	109	76	37
LEBRM	119	61	42
LEBRAM	120	65	37
MECC	83	64	75

Figure 4.15. A comparison of Diehard results between the proposed algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) and the previously presented MECC algorithm [19].

4.7. The Benefits of Using the LZ4 Compression Algorithm

Table 4.14 shows the difference in ciphertext size, encryption time, and decryption time between the use of LZ4 compression with the LEBM algorithm and without using any compression algorithm with the LEBM algorithm. The results were achieved using the computer-A.

Table 4.14. (a) Ciphertext size, encryption time, and decryption time for the LEBM algorithm without any compression algorithm.

Plaintext size (B)	Ciphertext size (B)	Encryption time (ms)	Decryption time (ms)
609	657	109.7	96.9
25,615	25657	141	145.3
35,080	35121	161.9	185.1
61,386	61433	211.5	244.3
184,162	184209	410.5	399.6

Table 4.14. (b) Ciphertext size, encryption time, and decryption time for the LEBM algorithm using the LZ4 compression algorithm.

Plaintext size (B)	Ciphertext size (B)	Encryption time (ms)	Compression time (μs)	Decryption time (ms)	Decompression time (μs)
609	529	107.6	39.5	91	67.5
25,615	16937	133.7	177.4	115.3	118.6
35,080	22969	143.4	213.9	126	147.6
61,386	39321	168.8	360	153.3	184.1
184,162	116113	294.9	917.1	290.6	344.3

The results show that LZ4 compression has significant benefits for reducing the ciphertext size, encryption time, and decryption time.

Additionally, the Diehard tests were applied to all proposed algorithms (LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM) with and without the use of the LZ4 compression algorithm, as illustrated in table 4.15 and corresponding figure 4.16. The test was done using a random readable text file of 24.8 MB size, which introduced a ciphertext of 10.7 MB size due to the LZ4 compression algorithm. It has a compression ratio of 2.3.

Table 4.15. A comparison between the use of LZ4 with LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM and without using any compression algorithm.

algorithms	safe	doubt	failure
LEBM without compression	111	60	51
LEBM with compression	109	76	37
LEBRM without compression	105	63	54
LEBRM with compression	119	61	42
LEBRAM with compression	110	67	45
LEBRAM without compression	120	65	37

Figure 4.16. A comparison between the use of LZ4 with LEBM, LEBRM, and LEBRAM and without using any compression algorithm.

The results show that the compression reduces the number of failure p -values, which means it improves the randomness of ciphertexts, leading to make the proposed algorithms more secure.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

5.1. Conclusions

- The LZ4 compression algorithm decreases the processing time by decreasing the plaintext size. Also, it increases the security level by increasing the randomness of the ciphertext.
- Using the Blowfish algorithm for encryption in the LEBM hybrid algorithm provides a high-security level. Furthermore, it is simple to implement.
- Using the RC4 and Blowfish algorithms for encryption in the LEBRM hybrid algorithm decreases the processing time with a slight decrease in security level.
- Using the RC4, Blowfish and AES algorithms for encryption in the LEBRAM algorithm decreases the processing time and provides the highest security level compared to others. In addition, the processing timeline with huge ciphertext size increased quite a bit rather than the LEBM and LEBRM hybrid algorithms.
- Using the Raspberry Pi as a WSN node fits a large number of WSNs applications due to its numerous technical specifications, which are not found in other types of nodes. Its only disadvantage is that it consumes more power than others.

5.2. Future Work

- Formulating a model of WSNs' energy consumption when using LEBM, LEBRM, or LEBRAM for security by using a network simulator or practical WSN.

- Designing a novel security algorithm that achieves other security objectives like availability and freshness.
- Reducing the power consumption of the Raspberry Pi.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Shukla, "Security Issues, Challenges and Solutions For Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN): A Review", *Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, Vol. 11, No. 2, 2020.
- [2] P. K. Singh, B. K. Bhargava, M. Paprzycki, N. C. Kaushal, and W. C. Hong, "Handbook of Wireless Sensor Networks: Issues and Challenges in Current Scenario's", first edition, Springer Nature, Switzerland, 2020.
- [3] D. Suhag, S. S. Gaur, and A. K. Mohapatra, "A proposed scheme to achieve node authentication in military applications of wireless sensor network", *Journal of Statistics and Management Systems*, Vol. 22, No. 2, 2019.
- [4] G. Tejpal, and S. Sharma, "A survey article on attacks and security goals in Wireless Sensor Networks", In *2017 2nd International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES)*, IEEE publishing, 2017.
- [5] M. A. Matin, "Wireless sensor networks: Technology and protocols", first edition, InTech, Croatia, 2012.
- [6] M. Panda, "Security in wireless sensor networks using cryptographic techniques", *American Journal of Engineering Research (AJER)*, Vol. 3, No. 1, 2014.
- [7] M. Dener, "Security analysis in wireless sensor networks", *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks*, Vol. 10, No.10, 2014.
- [8] G. Sharma, S. Bala, and A. K. Verma, "Security frameworks for wireless sensor networks-review", *2nd International Conference on Communication, Computing & Security [ICCCS-2012]*, *Procedia Technology* publishing, Vol. 6, 2012.

- [9] M. Elhoseny, X. Yuan, H. K. El-Minir, and A. M. Riad, "An energy efficient encryption method for secure dynamic WSN", *Security and Communication Networks*, Vol. 9, No. 13, 2016.
- [10] N. Garg, and P. Yadav, "Comparison of asymmetric algorithms in cryptography", *Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing (IJCSMC)*, Vol. 3, No. 4, 2014.
- [11] W. Ren, and Z. Miao, "A hybrid encryption algorithm based on DES and RSA in bluetooth communication", In 2010 Second International Conference on Modeling, IEEE publishing, 2010.
- [12] M. Bafandehkar, S. M. Yasin, R. Mahmood, and Z. M. Hanapi, "Comparison of ECC and RSA algorithm in resource constrained devices", In 2013 International Conference on IT Convergence and Security (ICITCS), IEEE publishing, 2013.
- [13] R. Rizk, and Y. Alkady, "Two-phase hybrid cryptography algorithm for wireless sensor networks", *Journal of Electrical Systems and Information Technology*, Vol. 2, No. 3, 2015.
- [14] D. Bhole, A. Mote, and R. Patil, "A new security protocol using hybrid cryptography algorithms", *International Journal of Computer Sciences and Engineering*, Vol. 4, No. 2, 2016.
- [15] M. Rajalakshmi, C. Parthasarathy and R.V. Indrajith, "Advanced Cryptographic Algorithm to Secure the Sensor Node Data in Wireless Sensor Networks", *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, Vol. 24, No. 6, 2016.
- [16] A. Pandey, and U. k. Lilhore, "An Improved AES Cryptosystem Based Genetic Method on S-Box, With, 256 Key Sizes and 14-Rounds", *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Science*, Vol. 4, No. 3, 2017.

- [17] S. Prakash, and A. Rajput, “Hybrid cryptography for secure data communication in wireless sensor networks”. In Ambient Communications and Computer Systems, Springer publishing, 2018.
- [18] K. M. Abdullah, E. H. Houssein, and H. H. Zayed, “New security protocol using hybrid cryptography algorithm for WSN”, In 2018 1st International Conference on Computer Applications & Information Security (ICCAIS), IEEE publishing, 2018.
- [19] S. M. Ali, “Hybrid Security Technique for Wireless Sensor Network”, MSc. Thesis, Computer Science Dept., Univ. of Babylon, Babylon, Iraq, 2019.
- [20] A. Tripathy, S. K. Pradhan, A. R. Tripathy, and A. K. Nayak, “A new hybrid cryptography technique in wireless sensor network”, Int. J. Innovative Technol. Exploring Eng. (IJITEE), Vol. 8, No. 10, 2019.
- [21] Pooja, and R. K. Chauhan, “Triple phase hybrid cryptography technique in a wireless sensor network”, International Journal of Computers and Applications, 2020.
- [22] O. E. M. Ebadati, F. Eshghi, and A. Zamani, “A Hybrid Encryption Algorithm for Security Enhancement of Wireless Sensor Networks: A Supervisory Approach to Pipelines”, Computer Modeling in Engineering & Sciences, Vol. 122, No. 1, 2020.
- [23] H. Modares, R. Salleh, and A. Moravejosharieh, “Overview of security issues in wireless sensor networks”, In 2011 third international conference on computational intelligence, IEEE publishing, 2011.
- [24] R. Muraleedharan, and L. A. Osadciw, “Balancing the performance of a sensor network using an ant system”, Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Vol. 67, 2003.
- [25] R. Muraleedharan, and L. A. Osadciw, “Jamming attack detection and countermeasures in wireless sensor network using ant system”, In

- Wireless Sensing and Processing, Proc. of SPIE publishing, Vol. 6248, 2006.
- [26] I. Tomić, and J. A. McCann, “A survey of potential security issues in existing wireless sensor network protocols”, IEEE Internet of Things Journal, Vol. 4, No. 6, 2017.
- [27] B. Narwal, and A. K. Mohapatra, “A survey on security and authentication in wireless body area networks”, Journal of Systems Architecture, Vol. 113, 2021.
- [28] R. Verma, and S. Bharti, “A Survey of Network Attacks in Wireless Sensor Networks”, In International Conference on Information, Springer publishing, 2020.
- [29] H. Tawalbeh, S. Hashish, L. Tawalbeh, and A. Aldairi, “Security in Wireless Sensor Networks Using Lightweight Cryptography”, Journal of Information Assurance & Security, Vol. 12, No. 4, 2017.
- [30] J. Borghoff, A. Canteaut, T. Güneysu, E. B. Kavun, M. Knezevic, L. R. Knudsen, G. Leander, V. Nikov, C. Paar, C. Rechberger, P. Rombouts, S. S. Thomsen, and T. Yalçın, “PRINCE—a low-latency block cipher for pervasive computing applications”, In International Conference on the Theory and Application of Cryptology and Information Security, Springer publishing, 2012.
- [31] N. Shefali, “Object-Oriented PL/SQL Programming : Creating Object Types and Methods in Oracle 10g”, CSI Communication, Vol. 37, No. 2, 2013.
- [32] K. Yang, “Wireless sensor networks”, first edition, Springer, London, 2014.
- [33] K. Karimi, and G. Atkinson, “What the Internet of Things (IoT) needs to become a reality”, White Paper, FreeScale and ARM, 2013.

- [34] A. M. Ali, and A. K. Farhan, “A novel improvement with an effective expansion to enhance the MD5 hash function for verification of a secure e-document”, IEEE Access, Vol. 8, 2020.
- [35] M. U. Bokhari, and Q. M. Shallal, “A review on symmetric key encryption techniques in cryptography”, International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 147, No. 10, 2016.
- [36] M. Bellare, K. G. Paterson, and P. Rogaway, “Security of symmetric encryption against mass surveillance”, In Annual Cryptology Conference, Springer publishing, 2014.
- [37] M. Agrawal, and P. Mishra, “A comparative survey on symmetric key encryption techniques”, International Journal on Computer Science and Engineering, Vol. 4, No. 5, 2012.
- [38] M. S. Iqbal, S. Singh, and A. Jaiswal, “Symmetric key cryptography: Technological developments in the field”, International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 117, No. 15, 2015.
- [39] M. A. Orumiehchiha, J. Pieprzyk, E. Shakour, and R. Steinfeld, “Cryptanalysis of RC4 (n, m) Stream Cipher”, In Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Security of Information and Networks, IACR publishing, 2013.
- [40] D. S. Abd Elminaam, H. M. Abdual-Kader, and M. M. Hadhoud, “Evaluating The Performance of Symmetric Encryption Algorithms”, Int. J. Netw. Secur., Vol. 10, No. 3, 2010.
- [41] A. Mousa, and A. Hamad, “Evaluation of the RC4 algorithm for data encryption”, Int. J. Comput. Sci. Appl., Vol. 3, No. 2, 2006.
- [42] J. M. Saadoon, and I. J. Mohammed, “ARSMS: A Hybrid Secured SMS Protocol for Smart Home using AES and RC4”, IJCSNS, Vol. 18, No. 2, 2018.

- [43] B. Schneier, “Description of a new variable-length key, 64-bit block cipher (Blowfish)”, In International Workshop on Fast Software Encryption, Springer publishing, 1993.
- [44] T. Nie, and T. Zhang, “A study of DES and Blowfish encryption algorithm”, In Tencon 2009-2009 IEEE Region 10 Conference, IEEE publishing, 2009.
- [45] A. Abdullah, “Advanced encryption standard (AES) algorithm to encrypt and decrypt data”, Cryptography and Network Security, Vol. 16, 2017.
- [46] X. Zhang, and K. K. Parhi, “High-speed VLSI architectures for the AES algorithm”, IEEE transactions on very large scale integration (VLSI) systems, Vol. 12, No. 9, 2004.
- [47] D. Bujari, and E. Aribas, “Comparative analysis of block cipher modes of operation”, In International Advanced Researches & Engineering Congress, 2017.
- [48] X. Hu, and Y. Zhao, “Block ciphers classification based on random forest”, In Journal of Physics: Conference Series, IOP Publishing, Vol. 1168, No. 3, 2019.
- [49] W. Diffie and M. Hellman, “New directions in cryptography”, IEEE transactions on Information Theory, Vol. 22, No. 6, 1976.
- [50] G. S. Quirino, A. R. Ribeiro, and E. D. Moreno, “Asymmetric encryption in wireless sensor networks”, IntechOpen, London, 2012.
- [51] U. SenthilKumar, and U. Senthilkumaran, “Review of asymmetric key cryptography in wireless sensor networks”, International Journal of Engineering and Technology, Vol. 8, No. 2, 2016.
- [52] V. Gupta, D. Stebila, S. Fung, S. C. Shantz, N. Gura, and H. Eberle, “Speeding up Secure Web Transactions Using Elliptic Curve Cryptography”, NDSS. 2004.

- [53] A. E. Beltrán, "IOT cryptography schemes comparison", MSc. Thesis, Telecommunications Eng. Dept., La Salle School of Electronics and Computer Engineering, Barcelona, Spain, 2018.
- [54] G. Gong, J. K. C. Gupta, "Progress in Cryptography - INDOCRYPT", 11th International Conference on Cryptology India, Springer publishing, 2010.
- [55] S. Al-Kuwari, J. H. Davenport, and R. J. Bradford, "Cryptographic Hash Functions: Recent Design Trends and Security Notions", IACR Cryptol. ePrint Arch., 2011.
- [56] R. Rivest, and S. Dusse, "The MD5 message-digest algorithm", MIT Laboratory for Computer Science and RSA Data Security 1992.
- [57] S. Gupta, N. Goyal, and K. Aggarwal, "A review of comparative study of md5 and ssh security algorithm", International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 104, No. 14, 2014.
- [58] S. Shanmugasundaram, and R. Lourdasamy, "A comparative study of text compression algorithms", International Journal of Wisdom Based Computing, Vol. 1, No. 3, 2011.
- [59] B. Carpentieri, "Efficient compression and encryption for digital data transmission", Security and Communication Networks, Vol. 2018, 2018.
- [60] M. Bartík, S. Ubik, and P. Kubalik, "LZ4 compression algorithm on FPGA", In 2015 IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Circuits, and Systems (ICECS), IEEE publishing, 2015.
- [61] W. Liu, F. Mei, C. Wang, M. O'Neill, and E. E. Swartzlander, "Data compression device based on modified LZ4 algorithm", IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics, Vol. 64, No. 1, 2018.
- [62] R. D. Masram, "Efficient Selection of Compression-Encryption Algorithms for Securing Data Based on Various Parameters", MSc.

Thesis, Computer Eng. And IT Dept., College of Engineering, Pune, India, 2014.

- [63] J. Bellamy, “Randomness of D sequences via diehard testing”, arXiv preprint arXiv, 2013.
- [64] A. Doğanaksoy, F. Sulak, M. Uğuz, O. Şeker, and Z. Akcengiz, “New statistical randomness tests based on length of runs”, *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2015.
- [65] Y. Wang, and T. Nicol, “Statistical properties of pseudo random sequences and experiments with PHP and Debian OpenSSL”, In *European Symposium on Research in Computer Security*, Springer publishing, 2014.
- [66] P. S. Ramesh, F. Priya, and B. Santhi, “Review on security protocols in wireless sensor networks”, *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, Vol. 38, No. 1, 2012.
- [67] V. Vujović, and M. Maksimović, “Raspberry Pi as a Wireless Sensor node: Performances and constraints”, In *2014 37th International Convention on Information and Communication Technology, MIPRO 2014* publishing, 2014.

APPENDICES

Appendix A: publications' Acceptance Letters

Republic of Iraq
Ministry of Higher Education
And Scientific Research
University of Kerbala
Dean Office

جمهورية العراق
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
جامعة كربلاء
مكتب عميد الكلية العلمية

No : 73 / 5 / م
date : 2021 / 6 / 28

العدد : م / 5 / 73
التاريخ : 28 / 6 / 2021

Subject: Paper Publishing Acceptance

Dear Hudhaifa Abdulhameed, Ayoob Abdulhameed, Mahmood Mosleh,
Alhamzah Mohammad

We are delighted to inform you that your manuscript entitled “**Lightweight Security Protocol for WSNs using Hybrid Cryptography Algorithm**” has been accepted in the 9th International Conference of Applied Science and Technology (ICAST2021) Conference Proceeding.

The accepted manuscripts will be published in the AIP conference proceedings which is Scopus indexed and has an impact factor.

Once your article is uploaded online, a notification email will be sent to you.

If you have any enquiry, please, do not hesitate to contact us.

Yours Sincerely,

Jasim Alawadi

Assist. Prof. Dr. Jasim Hanoon Hashim Al-Awadi
Chairman of ICAST 2021
Dean of the Faculty of Science, University of Kerbala, Karbala, Iraq.
Phone: +9647831556219
E-mail: jasem.h@uokerbala.edu.iq

Date: October 20, 2021
Paper ID: IICPS 252

LETTER OF ACCEPTANCE

Dear Authors,

On behalf of the IICPS -21 Committee, and based on the reviewers' evaluation after double blind peer review and Guest editors' approval we are pleased to inform you that your paper entitled

" A lightweight hybrid cryptographic algorithm for WSN security using the raspberry pi as a node"

Written

Hudhaifa A. Abdulhameed, Mahmood F. Mosleh, Alhamzah T. Mohammad, Ayoob A. Abdulhameed

Has been accepted and will be processed to publication in the **IOP Journal of Physics** (Online ISSN: 1742-6596, Print ISSN: 1742-6588, IICPS-2021). It is our pleasure to invite you to attend the Iraqi Academics Syndicate 2nd International Conference for Pure and Applied Sciences (IICPS), Babylon Branch, Babylon, Iraq at 14-15 November 2021 to present your paper. We congratulate you for your achievement, the technical details about the publication will be informed later. The publication of the accepted paper will be provided by the end of **January 2022**.

We Will encourage more quality submissions from you and your colleagues in future

Regards,

Prof. Dr. Shubham Sh. Sharma

Special Issue Guest Editor of IICPS

**JOURNAL OF PHYSICS:
CONFERENCE SERIES**
IOP Publishing

Caution: This Acceptance Letter Made by IICPS Conference Guest Editors and All Approval Inquiries Should Addressed to Editorial Board Committee of IICPS.

info.csase=u...@edas.info 25 Jan

to me, Mahmood ▾

Dear Mr. Hudhaifa Abdulhameed:

2022 CSASE hopes all is doing great with you!

This is to inform you that your paper #1570785992 entitled ('A Lightweight Hybrid Cryptographic Algorithm for WSNs Tested by the Diehard Tests and the Raspberry Pi') for 2022 CSASE has been accepted with Major revision.

Appendix B: Technical specifications of the Raspberry Pi 4 Model B

- programmable System On a Chip (SoC) Broadcom BCM2711, quad-core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit at 1.5GHz
- Synchronous Dynamic Random Access Memory (SDRAM) 4 GB LPDDR4-2400
- Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) 2.4 GHz and 5.0 GHz IEEE 802.11b/g/n/ac, Bluetooth 5.0, BLE
- True Gigabit Ethernet
- 2 Universal Serial Bus (USB) 3.0 ports, 2 USB 2.0 ports
- Fully backward compatible 40-pin General Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) connector
- 2 High-Definition Multimedia Interface (HDMI) micro ports supporting video resolution up to 4K 60Hz
- 2-way Mobile Industry Processor Interface (MIPI) Display Serial Interface (DSI) DSI / Camera Serial Interface (CSI) ports for camera and display
- Stereo audio output and composite video port, 4-pole
- Slot for Micro Secure Digital (MicroSD) card, for operating system and data storage
- Requires 5.1V, 3A power supply via USB-C or GPIO
- Power over Ethernet (PoE) enabled (requires PoE HAT)

Appendix C: The Proposed Algorithms

Algorithm 1: The LEBM encryption procedure.

Input: plaintext, bobPubKey

Output: data_encrypted (MD5 hashing + alicePubKey + blowfish ciphertext)

- SET curve TO get_curve('secp192r1')
- SET bobPubKey TO decompress_pubkey(bobPubKey)
- SET bobPubKey TO ECDH.Point(curve, int(bobPubKey[0:48], 16), int(bobPubKey[48:], 16))
- SET alicePrivKey TO ECDH.random(curve.field.n)
- SET alicePubKey TO alicePrivKey * curve.g
- SET alicePubKey TO compress(alicePubKey)
- SET aliceSharedKey TO alicePrivKey * bobPubKey
- SET aliceSharedKey TO compress(aliceSharedKey)
- SET Key TO aliceSharedKey
- SET compressed TO lz4.frame.compress(plaintext)
- WHILE len(compressed) % 8 != 0:
 - compressed=compressed+b"0"
- SET iv TO "8 random bytes" //initialization vector for blowfish
- SET data_encrypted TO blowfish.encrypt_cbc(compressed, Key, iv)
- SET data_encrypted TO alicePubKey + data_encrypted
- SET MD5 TO hash.md5(data_encrypted)

- SET data_encrypted TO MD5 + data_encrypted
- Send (data_encrypted)

Algorithm 2: The LEBM decryption procedure.

Input: data_encrypted (MD5 hashing + alicePubKey + blowfish ciphertext)

Output: plaintext

- SET MD5 TO hash.md5(data_encrypted[16:])
- Compare (MD5, data_encrypted[0:16]) if not equal show "error"
- SET curve TO get_curve('secp192r1')
- SET bobPrivKey TO ECDH.random(curve.field.n)
- SET bobPubKey TO bobPrivKey * curve.g
- SET alicePubKey TO data_encrypted[16:41]
- SET alicePubKey TO decompress_pubkey(alicePubKey)
- SET alicePubKey TO ECDH.Point(curve, int(alicePubKey[0:48], 16), int(alicePubKey[48:], 16))
- SET bobSharedKey TO bobPrivKey * alicePubKey
- SET bobSharedKey TO compress(bobSharedKey)
- GET iv From sender
- SET Key TO bobSharedKey
- SET data_decrypted TO
blowfish.decrypt_cbc(data_encrypted[41:41+lng1], Key, iv)

- SET decompressed TO lz4.frame.decompress(data_decrypted)
//plaintext

Algorithm 3: The LEBRM encryption procedure.

Input: plaintext, bobPubKey

Output: data_encrypted (MD5 hashing + alicePubKey + blowfish ciphertext + RC4 ciphertext)

- SET curve TO get_curve('secp192r1')
- SET bobPubKey TO decompress_pubkey(bobPubKey)
- SET bobPubKey TO ECDH.Point(curve, int(bobPubKey[0:48], 16), int(bobPubKey[48:], 16))
- SET alicePrivKey TO ECDH.random(curve.field.n)
- SET alicePubKey TO alicePrivKey * curve.g
- SET alicePubKey TO compress(alicePubKey)
- SET aliceSharedKey TO alicePrivKey * bobPubKey
- SET aliceSharedKey TO compress(aliceSharedKey)
- SET Key TO aliceSharedKey
- SET compressed TO lz4.frame.compress(plaintext)
- SET lng TO len(compressed)
- SET lng1 TO int(lng / 2)
- SET lng1 TO lng1 - (lng1 % 8)
- SET compressed1 TO compressed[0:lng1*2:2]

- SET compressed2 TO compressed[1:lng1*2:2] + compressed[lng1*2:]
- SET iv TO "8 random bytes" //initialization vector for blowfish
- SET data_encrypted1 TO blowfish.encrypt_cbc(compressed1, Key, iv)
- SET data_encrypted2 TO RC4.encrypt(compressed2, Key)
- SET data_encrypted TO alicePubKey + data_encrypted1 + data_encrypted2
- SET MD5 TO hash.md5(data_encrypted)
- SET data_encrypted TO MD5 + data_encrypted
- Send (data_encrypted)

Algorithm 4: The LEBRM decryption procedure.

Input: data_encrypted (MD5 hashing + alicePubKey + blowfish ciphertext + RC4 ciphertext)

Output: plaintext

- SET MD5 TO hash.md5(data_encrypted[16:])
- Compare (MD5, data_encrypted[0:16]) if not equal show "error"
- SET curve TO get_curve('secp192r1')
- SET bobPrivKey TO ECDH.random(curve.field.n)
- SET bobPubKey TO bobPrivKey * curve.g
- SET alicePubKey TO data_encrypted[16:41]
- SET alicePubKey TO decompress_pubkey(alicePubKey)

- SET alicePubKey TO ECDH.Point(curve, int(alicePubKey[0:48], 16), int(alicePubKey[48:], 16))
- SET bobSharedKey TO bobPrivKey * alicePubKey
- SET bobSharedKey TO compress(bobSharedKey)
- GET iv From Sender
- SET Key TO bobSharedKey
- SET lng TO len(data_encrypted[41:])
- SET lng1 TO int(lng / 2)
- SET lng1 TO lng1 - (lng1 % 8)
- SET data_decrypted1 TO
blowfish.decrypt_cbc(data_encrypted[41:41+lng1], Key, iv)
- SET data_decrypted2 TO RC4.decrypt(data_encrypted[41+lng1:],
Key)
- SET data_decrypted TO bytearray([0]*lng1*2)
- SET data_decrypted[0:lng1*2:2] TO data_decrypted1
- SET data_decrypted[1:lng1*2:2] TO data_decrypted2[0:lng1]
- SET data_decrypted TO data_decrypted+data_decrypted2[lng1:]
- SET decompressed TO lz4.frame.decompress(data_decrypted)
//plaintext

Algorithm 5: The LEBRAM encryption procedure.

Input: plaintext, bobPubKey

Output: data_encrypted (MD5 hashing + alicePubKey + blowfish ciphertext + RC4 ciphertext + AES ciphertext)

- SET curve TO get_curve('secp192r1')
- SET bobPubKey TO decompress_pubkey(bobPubKey)
- SET bobPubKey TO ECDH.Point(curve, int(bobPubKey[0:48], 16), int(bobPubKey[48:], 16))
- SET alicePrivKey TO ECDH.random(curve.field.n)
- SET alicePubKey TO alicePrivKey * curve.g
- SET alicePubKey TO compress(alicePubKey)
- SET aliceSharedKey TO alicePrivKey * bobPubKey
- SET aliceSharedKey TO compress(aliceSharedKey)
- SET Key TO aliceSharedKey
- SET compressed TO lz4.frame.compress(plaintext)
- SET lng TO len(compressed)
- SET lng1 TO int(lng / 3)
- SET lng1 TO lng1 - (lng1 % 16)
- SET compressed1 TO compressed[0:lng1*3:3]
- SET compressed3 TO compressed[2:lng1*3:3]
- SET compressed2 TO compressed[1:lng1*3:3] + compressed[lng1*3:]
- SET iv TO "8 random bytes" //initialization vector for blowfish
- SET iv2 TO "16 random bytes" //initialization vector for AES
- SET data_encrypted1 TO blowfish.encrypt_cbc(compressed1, Key, iv)

- SET data_encrypted2 TO RC4.encrypt(compressed2, Key)
- SET data_encrypted3 TO AES.encrypt_cbc(compressed3, Key[:16], iv2)
- SET data_encrypted TO alicePubKey + data_encrypted1 + data_encrypted2 + data_encrypted3
- SET MD5 TO hash.md5(data_encrypted)
- SET data_encrypted TO MD5 + data_encrypted
- Send (data_encrypted)

Algorithm 6: The LEBRAM decryption procedure.

Input: data_encrypted (MD5 hashing + alicePubKey + blowfish ciphertext + RC4 ciphertext + AES ciphertext)

Output: plaintext

- SET MD5 TO hash.md5(data_encrypted[16:])
- Compare (MD5, data_encrypted[0:16]) if not equal show "error"
- SET curve TO get_curve('secp192r1')
- SET bobPrivKey TO ECDH.random(curve.field.n)
- SET bobPubKey TO bobPrivKey * curve.g
- SET alicePubKey TO data_encrypted[16:41]
- SET alicePubKey TO decompress_pubkey(alicePubKey)
- SET alicePubKey TO ECDH.Point(curve, int(alicePubKey[0:48], 16), int(alicePubKey[48:], 16))
- SET bobSharedKey TO bobPrivKey * alicePubKey

- SET bobSharedKey TO compress(bobSharedKey)
- GET iv and iv2 From Sender
- SET Key TO bobSharedKey
- SET lng TO len(data_encrypted[41:])
- SET lng1 TO int(lng / 3)
- SET lng1 TO lng1 - (lng1 % 16)
- SET data_decrypted1 TO
blowfish.decrypt_cbc(data_encrypted[41:41+lng1], Key, iv)
- SET data_decrypted2 TO
RC4.decrypt(data_encrypted[41+lng1:41+lng-lng1], Key)
- SET data_decrypted3 TO AES.decrypt_cbc(data_encrypted[41+lng-
lng1:41+lng], Key[:16], iv2)
- SET data_decrypted TO bytearray([0]*lng1*3)
- SET data_decrypted[0:lng1*3:3] TO data_decrypted1
- SET data_decrypted[1:lng1*3:3] TO data_decrypted2[0:lng1]
- SET data_decrypted[2:lng1*3:3] TO data_decrypted3
- SET data_decrypted TO data_decrypted+data_decrypted2[lng1:]
- SET decompressed TO lz4.frame.decompress(data_decrypted)
//plaintext

الخلاصة

شبكات الاستشعار اللاسلكية (WSNs) عبارة عن عدد هائل من العقد الصغيرة المثبتة في بيئات قاسية ومعادية لمراقبة وجمع بيانات محددة. يتم تثبيت شبكات WSN لدعم هياكل الجسور، والرعاية الصحية، والروبوتات، والمراقبة البيئية، وما إلى ذلك، وتتميز شبكات WSN بقيود فريدة مثل الطاقة الشديدة، والمستوى الأكثر كثافة لنشر العقدة، وعدم موثوقية عُقد المستشعرات، وقيود الحساب والتخزين. يجب مراعاة هذه الخصائص قبل إجراء أي تعديلات. تكمن مشكلة نقل البيانات لشبكات WSN في أنها معرضة لهجمات مختلفة، لذا يجب تشفيرها. تلعب العديد من خوارزميات التشفير دورًا جيدًا في أمن البيانات لشبكات WSN مع مراعاة خصائصها. يحتوي التشفير على طريقتين للسرية: تقنيات المفتاح المتماثل والمفتاح غير المتماثل. لكن لا تزال هناك بعض المشاكل. على سبيل المثال، لتخزين المفتاح عبر جميع العقد في الشبكة، تحتاج تقنية المفتاح المتماثل إلى مزيد من التخزين، بينما تستغرق تقنية المفتاح غير المتماثل وقتًا أطول للحساب. لذلك يجب تعديلها لتلائم مواصفات WSN.

في هذه الرسالة، تم اقتراح ثلاث خوارزميات تشفير هجينة، وهي LEBM وLEBRM وLEBRAM لتوفير مستوى أمن عالي مع استهلاك منخفض للطاقة.

تحقق الخوارزميات المقترحة ثلاثة أهداف تشفير: السرية، وتحقيق الهوية، وسلامة المعلومة باستخدام خوارزميات Blowfish وRC4 وAES للتشفير؛ وخوارزمية ECDH لتوزيع المفاتيح؛ وخوارزمية MD5 لسلامة البيانات. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، يتم استخدام خوارزمية الضغط LZ4 لتقليل حجم النص، مما يؤدي إلى تقليل وقت المعالجة واستهلاك الطاقة.

تم حساب حجم النص المشفر وأوقات التشفير وفك التشفير وإنتاجية الخوارزميات المقترحة. كما تم تطبيق اختبار دايبهارد على الخوارزميات المقترحة. وعليه تم مقارنة النتائج بنتائج الأعمال التي سبق نشرها. تم اختبار كل خوارزمية مقترحة باستخدام جهازي كمبيوتر مكتوب عليهما "A و B" و Raspberry Pi. عند استخدام Raspberry Pi، تظهر النتائج أن LEBM وLEBRM وLEBRAM حققت أفضل النتائج مقارنة بالأعمال السابقة. يحتوي LEBRAM على 120 قيمة p في المنطقة الآمنة و37 قيمة p فقط في منطقة الفشل، وهو أعلى مستوى أمن. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، عندما يكون حجم النص هو 184162 بايت، يكون له أقل وقت معالجة مع وقت تشفير يبلغ 303.1 ميلي ثانية ووقت فك تشفير يبلغ 319.5 ميلي ثانية، مما يجعله مثاليًا للنصوص الكبيرة. من ناحية أخرى، عندما يكون حجم النص 609 بايت، فإن خوارزمية LEBRM لديها أقل وقت معالجة، مع وقت تشفير يبلغ 164.5 ميلي ثانية ووقت فك تشفير يبلغ 71.5 ميلي ثانية، مما يجعلها مثالية للنصوص الصغيرة. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، فإن LEBM هي أبسط خوارزمية من حيث البناء.

جمهورية العراق
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
الجامعة التقنية الوسطى
الكلية التقنية الهندسية الكهربائية

خوارزميات تشفير هجينة خفيفة الوزن لشبكات الاستشعار اللاسلكية

رسالة مقدمة الى

الكلية التقنية الهندسية الكهربائية – الجامعة التقنية الوسطى
جزءاً من متطلبات نيل درجة الماجستير في هندسة تقنيات الحاسوب

تقدم بها الطالب

حذيفة عبدالمنعم عبدالحميد

بإشراف

أ.د. محمود فرحان مصلح

أ.م. الحمزة طاهر محمد

جمادى الآخرة 1443